

I-CATALOGUE *ye-species*

Ukuphuhlisa izakhono zoluntu lwasekuhlaleni kwi-Agroforestry
yesiNtu kummandla wase-Amadiba eMpuma Mpondoland

IDATHA YEMETADATA

Iveliso yesi-1 kaJanuwari 2025 yeProjekthi yeGreat Green Wall Initiative exhaswa yi-GEF Small Grants Programme ye-Great Green Wall Initiative iphunyezwe ngu ye-United Nations Development Programme.

Igama leProjekthi: Ukuphuhlisa izakhono zoluntu lwemveli kwi-agroforestry kwiNdawo yase-Amadiba eMpuma Mpondoland.

Inombolo yesalathiso seProjekthi: SAF/SGP/OP7/Y4/CORE/GGW/2024/06

Umbhali: Mallika Sardeshpande

Imifanekiso: Anele Mthembu (Institute of Natural Resources), Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist, iSpotnature, PlantZAfrica, Wikimedia Commons

Ucwangciso imbonakalo no yilo: Tracy Freese, Purple Boa Creations

Ukuguqulelwa kulwimi lwesiMpondo: Mxolisi Ngongoma no Sinegugu Zukulu (Sustaining the Wild Coast okanye Mazibuy' emasisweni)

I mithombo yolwazi eqinisekisiweyo:

Fox, F.W., & Norwood Young, M.E. (1982). Food from the Veld: edible plants of South Africa. Delta Books, Johannesburg. ISBN 0908387326.

PlantZAfrica <http://pza.sanbi.org/>

Useful Tropical Plants <http://tropical.theferns.info/>

World Agroforestry Centre <https://apps.worldagroforestry.org/treedb/>

Iprojekthi lusebenziswano phakathi kwe-Institute of Natural Resources (INR), i-Sustaining the Wild Coast (SWC), kunye ne-Siyasisiza Trust (ST). Kolu sebezniswano, i-INR izisa ulwazi lwezenzululwazi kunye nobuchwephesha malunga neentlobo zezityalo eziphuma kwi-agroforestry yemveli, i-SWC inika amakhonkco kunye namaqonga oluntu lwemveli lwendawo, kwaye i-ST izisa ubuchule bobugcisa kwiziseko ze-agroecology ezimiswe kule ndawo.

Ukwamkelwa: Iqela leprojekthi libulela kakhulu i-Farmers Forum, amalungu e-SWC, kunye ne-ST ngokulungiselela nokulawula iindibano ze workshops kunye nokutyala, kuquka unxibelelwano, ezothutho, ukulungiselela ukutya, kunye nokulungelelanisa imizamo yoluntu. Sibulela kakhulu kuluntu lwasekuhlaleni ngokwamkela kwabo ngobubele, ukuthatha inxaxheba kwabo, kunye nokusebenza kwabo ngokufanelekileyo ekutyaleni. Sikwavuma umbulelo kwi-UNDP GEF Small Grants Programme ngenkxaso-mali yalo msebenzi.

Le catalogue ibonisa ulwazi ngeentlobo eziluncedo zezihlahla okanye imithi ezityaliweyo njengexalenye yeprojekthi kwindawo yaseAmadiba eMzantsi Afrika. Ezizihlahla zikhula ngokwemvelo kwindawo, ezininzi zazo zineziqhamo ezinokutyiwa kunye nenxalenye yezokunyanga, kwaye zonke zineenzuzo kwi-agroforestry ezifana nokunikezela ngomthunzi, ukuthintela umoya, okanye ukuvelisa iinkuni.

Le catalogue inikezela ngolwazi malunga nesihlahla ngasinye kulencwadana. Iphaneli yangaphambili esecaleni ngasekhohlo ichaza indawo yemvelo kunye neempawu zentlalo, ikwabonisa izinto ezibalulekileyo xa kutyulwa emakhaya. Iphaneli yangaphambili esecaleni lasekunene ibonisa izinto ezityiwayo, ezonyango, i-agroforestry, kunye neenzuzo zespecies. Kwiphepha elingasemva elisezantsi ngasekhohlo kukho ulwazi malunga neemeko ezikhoyo kwindalo kwezinye izinto, ezifana nokusetyenziswa kwezinto kwihlabathi jikelele kunye nobudlelwane bazo nezilwanyana zasendle. Iphepha elingasemva elisezantsi kwesokunene libonisa iimeko ezithile ezifunwa ukuze ezi ntlalo zikhule kwaye zikhule kwakhona.

Le catalogue ingafundwa kunye neencwadi zokunyamekela izityalo ezaphuhlisa njengexalenye yeprojekthi, ezibonelela ngemigaqo jikelele malunga nokutyala, ukunakekelwa nokugcinwa, ukusetyenziswa okuzinzileyo, kunye nokwandiswa kwazo.

ISITSHIXO KWIISIMBOLI

Ubude bomthi / ukusasazeka komthi

Umthi

Isihlahla

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

Ubungakanani besiqhamo

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinambuzane

Ungcoliseko lamagqabi

Iintaka

Ubungakanani bempande

Izilwanyana

Ixesha lokutyala

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Amabakala/iimeko

Akukho

Ixesha lasekwindla

Low

Ixesha lasebusika

Phakathi

Ixesha lentwasahlabo

Phezulu

AMATHUNGULA

Carissa bispinosa (L), Forest num-num (E), amathungula (X)

Amathungula afumaneka kulo lonke elaseMzantsi Afrika kwiindawo ezinehlathi, emaphethelweni ehlathi, nakwiinduli zolwandle, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-1,600m.

Isiqhamo esimalunga ne-1cm ububanzi sikhula ngamaqela, kwaye singatyiwa siluhlaza, senziwe ijusi okanye ijem, ijeli, kwaye sisenokusetyenziswa ukwenza iwayini emnandi.

Lo mthi omaphakathi ukhula malunga ne-3m ukuphakama, ube ngumthi onameva okanye ube sisihlahlana esiminxeneyo esinegqabi elixineneyo.

Ngenxa yokuba unongcoliseko oluncinci lamagqabi kunye neengcambu ezingaqinanga kakhulu, ungalanyelwa okanye unokutyalwa kufutshane neentambo zombane namanzi, kunye nezakhiwo neendlela.

IXESHA LOKUQHAMBA			
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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Utyebile kwi-vitamin C, esinceda ekugcineni impilo entle yengqondo, yeenwele, yehomoni nolusu okanye isikhumba.

Ungumthombo omkhulu we-magnesium kunye ne-phosphorus, ezibalulekileyo ekusebenzeni kwemisipha namathambo.

Isiqhamo siqulethe ii-antioxidants eziluncedo kwimpilo entle kunye nokuphilisa izifo.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Ukhula ube ngumqolo ocacileyo ohlangeneyo okanye udonga oluphilayo olukwavalela izilwanyana ukuze zingangeni kwizinto ezityaliweyo.

Iingcambu zisetyenziswa kunyango lwemveli ukunyanga iintlungu, izifo zesifuba, amehlo, isisu, kunye nezifo ezosulelayo.

Xa utyalwe waxinana, wenza isithinteli somoya esihle kuba umelana nomoya onamandla.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Izinambuzane, ngakumbi amabhabhathane, ziyandwendwela iintyatyambo zalo.

Iintaka zithanda iziqhamo, kwaye ezinye ziyazalela ngenxa yamasebe azikhuselayo.

Esisihlahla esomeleleyo sihlala siluhlaza unyaka wonke kwaye sikwakwazi ukumelana nexesha lokoma.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/carissa-bispinosa>
 Imifanekiso: PlantZAfrica, iNaturalist,
 Wikimedia Commons

AMATHUNGULA

Carissa bispinosa (L), Forest num-num (E), amathungula (X)

Amathungula avela kunxweme olusempuma yeMzantsi Afrika kwaye ayafumaneka kwiindawo ze-Albany thicket, fynbos, grassland, Indian Ocean coastal belt, savanna, Succulent Karoo, kunye ne-Nama Karoo.

Amagqabi awo asisidlo samabhabhathane, iintyatyambo ezimnandi zitsala izinambuzane neentaka, kwaye izilwanyana ezinkulu zitya iziqhamo.

Ukuhanjiswa kwembewu kwenziwa ziinyosi, ngelixa imbewu isasazwa ziintaka ezityayo iziqhamo.

Ukuhlwayelwa kwembewu kufuneka kwenziwe ngembewu ethe yavuthwa, ngokususa inyama ekhusele imbewu.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Esi sihlahla siphumelela kakuhle kwimimandla eshushu ne-subtropical enobushushu obuphakathi kwe-25°C.

Silungele imvula ephakathi ne phakamileyo (800-1,200mm), kodwa siyakwazi ukumelana neemeko ezingalinganiyo ze-600mm ukuya kwi-1,800mm.

Sithanda ilanga elipheleleyo kodwa sinokunyamezela isithunzi esincinci.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Sityeba kakuhle kumhlaba onentlabathi okanye otyebileyo kwaye singathanda namanye amathambeka anamanzi aphumlayo.

Umhlaba ofanelekileyo une-pH ye-6.5, kodwa sinokunyamezela amaxabiso aphakathi kwe-5 ne-8.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Esi sihlahla sinokukhuliswa kwimbewu okanye kwiingcambu ezitsaliweyo eziphathiswe ngehmoni zokukhula.

Imbewu eqokelelwe kumthi onempilo iza kuhluma phakathi kweenyanga ezi-2.

Izityalo eziselula azidingi nkcenkchesho eninzi.

Isantya sokukhula siphakathi kwe-300mm ukuya kwi-1.2m nkonyaka kwaye sifikelela ekuvuthweni phakathi kweminyaka emi-2 ukuya kwe-3.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/carissa-bispinosa>
 Imifanekiso: PlantZAfrica, iNaturalist,
 Wikimedia Commons

AMATHUNGULA

Carissa edulis (L), simple-spined num-num (E), amathungula (X)

Amathungula anemisipha elula afumaneka kumbindi nakumazantsi eAfrika, aqhele ukubakho nakwimithana ekufuphi nolwandle, ukuya kubude obungange-2,000m.

Iziqhamo ezimalunga ne-1cm ziveliswa ngamakhama okanye amaqela phakathi kukaDisemba noFebruwari kwaye zidlwa ziraw, ziyijusi, okanye zenziwe ijemu.

Lomthana ugutyungelwe ngamahlala kwaye unokufikelela kubude obuyi-5m. Njengoko ukhula ngokusasazeka, ufaneleke kakhulu ukwenziwa isithintelo sendalo esinesihlahla esikhulayo kunye neentyatyambo ezinencasa emnandi.

Ngenxa yokuba inengcambu ezingekho nzulu kunye namagqabi aphantsi, ifaneleke ukuba ityalwe kufutshane nezikolo, izakhiwo, iindlela, kunye nemigca yezixhobo zombane.

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Jun	Jul	Aug	❄️	
Sep	Oct	Nov	🦋	

IMPILO NOKUTYA

Iqulethe i-vitamin C, ebalulekileyo ekugcineni impilo yengqondo, iinwele, amahomoni nolusu.

Iyimithombo etyebileyo ye-calcium, i-iron, i-magnesium kunye ne-zinc, ekomelezeni amathambo nakwimpilo yegazi.

Iingcambu zisetyenziswa kunyango lomhlaza, imalariya, izifo zesifuba nokungaphatheki kakuhle kwesisu, ixhaphake kakhulu njengesiyobisi sokunciphisa iintlungu.

Iziqhamo ziluncedo ekunyangeni isifo sotyatyazo esinzima.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Esisihlahla sinameva singatyalwa njengesithintelo isiphilayo okanye uthango lokhuseleko.

Iinkuni ngamanye amaxesha zisetyenziswa njengamafutha okubasa umlilo.

Iziqhamo zinokuxutywa zenziwe iwayini, okanye i-veegar.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Ezinye iintaka ziyayisebenzisa ukwenza izidleke kuzo ngenxa yokomelela kwayo.

Iziqhamo namagqabi zityiwa ziintaka ezininzi, iimfene kunye neentlobo ezininzi zezilwanyana.

Isityalo sinika ukhuseleko kwizilwanyana ezincinci nakwiinyoka.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/carissa-edulis>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist

AMATHUNGULA

Carissa edulis (L), simple-spined num-num (E), amathungula (X)

Esisihlahla sivele eAfrika eshushu kwaye sifumaneka kwimimandla yehlathi elimalunga noLwandle lwaseIndiya (Indian ocean).

Sisityalo esixhasa ubuninzi beentlobo zezinto eziphilayo: iintaka, amaKudu, iiNyala, amaBushbuck, iilmpala kunye neeMpunzi ziyazithanda iziqhamo namagqabi, ngelixa iintaka neenyoka ezifuna indawo yokuzimela zizifumana phantsi kwemithi exineneyo.

Ukunwenwa kwesisihlahla kwenziwa ziinyosi, kwaye imbewu isasazwa ziintaka nezilwanyana ezitya iziqhamo. Imbewu ingagcinwa ukuya kuthi ga kwiinyanga ezili-12.

Ngenxa yokuba itsala iintaka, izinambuzane kunye nezilwanyana, kungcono ukuyityala kude nekhaya.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Esisihlahla siyakwazi ukumelana nemozulu eyahlukeneyo, kodwa sithanda ubushushu obufanelekileyo ukusuka kwi-19°C ukuya kwi-30°C.

Sikhula ngcono kwimvula ephakathi kwe-1,000mm ne-1,300mm ngonyaka.

Sithanda ukukhanya kwelanga ngokupheleleyo kwaye siyaxhathisa ekunqandeni kwamanzi.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Esisihlahla sithanda umhlaba onetyuwa encinci (loamy) ophuma amanzi kakuhle.

Siyakwazi ukumelana nepH ukusuka kwi-alkaline ukuya kwi-asidi.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Isityalo siyakwazi ukuveliswa ngokusikwa okanye ngembewu ecocekileyo.

Imbewu idla ngokuhluma phakathi kweentsuku ezi-7 nezi-14.

Izithole nezityalo ezisencinci azixhathisi ikhephu elinzima.

Sifuna amanzi aphakathi ukuze sikhule kakuhle.

Isityalo sikhula phakathi kwe-1 ukuya kwi-2m ngonyaka kwaye sifikelela ekuvuthweni phakathi kweminyaka emi-4 nemi-5.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/carissa-edulis>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist

AMATHUNGULA

Carissa macrocarpa (L), big num-num, Natal plum (E), amathungula (X)

Amathungula afumaneka kunxweme olusempuma lwe-Afrika naseMzantsi Afrika, aqhele ukubakho kumahlathi asecaleni kolwandle, kumahlathi aselunxwemeni, nakwiindunduma zesanti, kwiindawo ezahlukeneyo zobude kunye nobuzani.

Isiqhamo esinye esimalunga ne-5cm, ukusuka ngoMatshi ukuya kuOkthobha, siyathandwa kwaye siyadliwa si raw, ijusi okanye senziwe ijemu.

Esisihlahla sikhula kancinci sivelisa amagqabi amaninzi kwaye asidluli i-2m ubude.

Indlela esikhulayo ngayo, amahlala kunye neengcambu, kuyenza sifanelekele ukutyalwa kufutshane nezakhiwo, iindlela kunye nezixhobo zombane.

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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Iquletke i-vitamin C enceda ekugcineni impilo yengqondo, iinwele, amahomoni kunye nolusu.

Iyimithombo emihle ye-magnesium kunye ne-phosphorus, ezibalulekileyo ekusebenzeni kwamathambo kunye nezihlunu.

Iquletke ifayibha kunye neprotheyini ezibalulekileyo kumandla kunye nokugcina inkqubo yokwetyisa isempilweni.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Izihlahla zixabisekile ekwenzeni ijemu kunye nejeli ezimnandi.

Iinyosi ziyayithanda kwaye ziyanceda ekufumaneni i-pollen, nto leyo efanelekileyo kwabo bagcina iinyosi.

Ngenxa yobuhle obuqaqambileyo intyantyambo nohlaza lwayo, ingumfanekiso omhle kwaye inokusetyenziswa kumagadi.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Iintyantyambo neziqhamo zitsala impukane, amabhabhathane kunye neentaka.

Inameva ayimela, nto leyo eyenza ikhule njengesithintelo esihle nesingenakugqithwa.

Esisihlahla asiphumi mthubi kwaye siyaxhathisa ekunqandeni kwamanzi.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/carissa-macrocarpa>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes

AMATHUNGULA

Carissa macrocarpa (L), big num-num, Natal plum (E), amathungula (X)

Amathungula avela kunxweme olusempuma loMzantsi Afrika, afumaneka kumahlathi axutyiweyo aseAlbany nakumahlathi asecaleni koLwandlekazi lwase Indian ocean.

Isityalo esibalulekileyo ekuzaliseni iintlobo ngeentlobo zezinto eziphilayo, sinceda iinyosi eziphunga ivumba leentyatyambo kunye neentaka ezidla iziqhamo zaso.

Esisihlahla yi-dioecious, oko kuthetha ukuba isityalo ngasinye siveza iintyatyambo zesini esinye kuphela (ezibhinqileyo okanye ezidodana), kwaye sixhomekeke kwiimpukane (pollination) ukuze ziphathise uthuli lweentyatyambo.

Kungcono ukutyala izityalo ezininzi kunye ukuze kukhuthazwe ukuveliswa kweziqhamo.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Isityalo sixhathisa imozulu ephakathi kwe-23°C ukuya kwi-28°C, kodwa sinokumelana nobushushu obuphakathi kwe-10°C kunye ne-34°C.

Sithanda imvula ephakathi kwe-800mm ne-1,200mm, kodwa sinokumelana ne-600mm ukuya kwi-1,800mm.

Sithanda ukukhanya kwelanga ngokupheleleyo, kodwa sinokukhula kwindawo enesiqingatha somthunzi.

Sithanda iindawo ezifudumeleyo kwaye sibuthathaka ekubandeni okubukhali.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Esisihlahla sithanda umhlaba onetyuwa encinci (loamy).

Siyakwazi ukumelana nepH phakathi kwe-5 kunye ne-8.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Singakhuliswa ngembewu, ngamatyathanga afakwe iihomoni okanye ngendlela yokufaka ingcambu kumhlaba (layering).

Izityalo eziselula zifuna ukufumanzwa amanzi aphaakathi (moderate).

Sikhula ukusuka kwi-700mm ukuya kwi-1000mm ngonyaka kwaye sifikelela kwixesha lokuvuthwa emva kweminyaka emithathu.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/carissa-macrocarpa>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes

IBOZA

Tetradenia riparia (L), ginger bush, misty plume bush (E), iboza (X)

Esisihlahla sifumaneka kunxweme olusempuma lweMzantsi Afrika, emilanjani, ekupheleni kwehlahlathi, kwiinduli ezomileyo ezinehlahlathi, nakwiindawo ezingafumani iliqhwa kakhulu, ukuya kutsho kwi-1,800m.

Iziqhamo zikhula njengepod enembewu kwiintyatyambo zesityalo esilini, kwaye azidliwa.

Esi sityalo sikhula ngokukhawuleza size sifikelele kubude obumalunga ne-3m, sivelise izityalo ezimangalisayo zeentyatyambo ezimaube ekupheleni kobusika.

Isityalo singakhuliswa kufutshane nezakhiwo, iindlela, imibhobho yamanzi kunye nemigca yamandla ngenxa yengcambu engangeni kakubi okanye kakhulu emhlabeni.

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Sep	Oct	Nov	🦋	

IMPILO NOKUTYA

Esi sityalo sithandwa kakhulu ngenxa yeempawu zaso zonyango kwaye sesisetyenziswe kwiminyaka ngeminyaka ukunceda kwiingxaki zokuphefumla, iintlungu zesisu kunye nentloko.

Amagqabi acudisiweyo ayabiliswa kwaye asetyenziselwa ukunyanga izifo ezininzi ezifana notyatyazo, idropsy, ifiva, i-flu, imalariya, i-dengue fever, isifo samazinyo, nezinye izifo ezahlukeneyo.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Esi sityalo sisihombiso esihle kakhulu ebusika xa iintyatyambo ezimaube zibangela umbono obalaseleyo xa ezinye izityalo zingekahombisi.

Amasebe aphila kakuhle emanzini kwaye alungele ukulungiswa kweentyatyambo.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Iintyatyambo zesi sityalo zityebile kwi-nectar, zitsala izinambuzane ezininzi ezinceda ekuzaleni kweentyatyambo, kwaye sisityalo esibalulekileyo sokutya iinyosi ebusika.

Iintaka ezitya izinambuzane zitsalwa linani elikhulu lezinambuzane ezityelela iintyatyambo.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/tetradenia-riparia>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

IBOZA

Tetradenia riparia (L), ginger bush, misty plume bush (E), iboza (X)

Esi sityalo sivela kumbindi naseMzantsi Afrika kwaye sifumaneka kwi-savanna biome.

Iintyatyambo zawo zivela ngobuninzi kwaye utsala izinambuzane ezithanda incindi, usisondlo kwizibungu.

Esisihlahla sinesini esingafaniyo, oko kuthetha ukuba isityalo ngasinye siveza iintyatyambo zodwa zomfazi okanye ezendoda.

Izinambuzane zenza uphuhliso lweentyatyambo, ezikhula zibe ziintyatyambo eziya kuba zizinqhamo kwiintyatyambo zesityalo somfazi.

Kungcono ukutyala izityalo ezininzi kunye ukuze kukhuthazwe uphuhliso lweentyatyambo, iziqhamo kunye nokufuneka kwemithombo yembewu.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Isityalo sithanda imozulu eshushu, ephakathi kwe-subtropical ne-tropical.

Iindawo ezinemvula encinci yonyaka zilungele ukukhula kwaso.

Sikhula kakuhle xa sityalwe elangeni elipheleleyo.

Singamelana nomkhenkce omncinci, kodwa siyavakalelwa yindawo ebandayo kakhulu.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Sithanda umhlaba ohamba kakuhle amanzi, ongumhlaba otyebileyo, onodongwe oluncinci okanye onesanti.

Ukuthetha umhlaba onepH ephakathi kwe-6.5.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Kungcono ukusikhulisa sisebenzisa izithole eziphathiswe iihomoni, ezikhula lula kwaye zinokutyalwa unyaka wonke.

Esisihlahla sifuna amanzi aphakathi ehlotyeni, kwaye amancinci ebusika.

Xa sele sikhule kakuhle, sikhula malunga ne-80cm ngonyaka, kwaye izakuqhakaza kunyaka wayo wokuqala.

Isityalo siyazuza xa sisikwa emva kwexesha lokuqhakaza.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/tetradenia-riparia>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

IGQWANITSHA

Portulacaria afra (L), porkbush, elephant's foot (E), igqwanitsha (X)

Esi sityalo sifumaneka kwiindawo ezifudumeleyo zaseMzantsi Afrika, siqheleke kwiinduli ezinamatye, iindawo ezinehlathi elincinci, amahlathi aqinileyo, i-bushveld, kunye nemilanjana eyomileyo.

IGqwanitsha ayaziwa kakhulu ngeziqhamo, ezingenakutyiwa, kodwa inika izibonelelo ezininzi kwimpilo nakwimeko-bume.

Sisihlahlana esihlala siluhlaza unyaka wonke kwaye asidluli umphakamo weemitha ezi-3. Sisityalo esinomphunga oqinileyo, kwaye amasebe aso asakazeka esezantsi.

Inkqubo yeengcambu zaso ezincinci, kunye nokuphakama kwaso, kwenza kube kufanelekile ukusityala kufutshane nezakhiwo, imibhobho yamanzi, imigca yamandla neendlela.

IXESHA LOKUQHAMBA

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

IMPILO NOKUTYA

Esi sityalo sinceda oomama abasakuncancisa ukuba bandise ubisi lwabo.

Amagqabi anciphisa unxano kwaye aluncedo ekunyangeni ukudinwa, ukufudumala ngokugqithisileyo kunye nokoma emzimbeni.

Ukuluma amagqabi kunyangisa iintlungu zomqala kunye nezifo zomlomo.

Ijusi yaso isetyenziselwa ukunyangama achokoza, ukunciphisa amabala eluswini.

Amagqabi agrayiweyo anciphisa iintlungu zomnwe oqaqambayo kunye neenzwane.

Ijusi yaso isetyenziswa njenge-antiseptic kwaye ilungile ekunyangeni ukutshiswa lilanga.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Esi sityalo sisidlo sezilwanyana ezifuywayo.

Iintyatyambo ezityebileyo kwi-nectar zitsala iinyosi.

Sinokutyalwa njenge-heji eqinileyo okanye uthango lokhuseleko.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Ihlathi elixineneyo lamasebe aso libonelela ngendawo efanelekileyo yokuhlala iintaka.

Sisetyenziswa ekulweni ukuqhwalala komhlaba nakwimisebenzi yokubuyisela umhlaba.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/portulacaria-afra>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

IGQWANITSHA

Portulacaria afra (L), porkbush, elephant's foot (E), igqwanitsha (X)

IGqwanitsha livela eMzantsi Afrika kwaye lifumaneka kwiAlbany Thicket, iFynbos, i-Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, iNama Karoo, kunye neSucculent Karoo biomes.

Lidlala indima ebalulekileyo kwindalo njengomthombo wokutya kwizilwanyana. Lidliwa kakhulu ziinkomo zasandle, iingwenya, iinkamela zamanzi, neenkomo ezifuywayo.

Nangona imbewu yaso isasazwa ziintaka, indlela esebenzayo yokulinywa kukusebenzisa amahlumela unyaka wonke.

Lityalwa zizilwanyana neenyosi, kwaye kufuneka lityalwe kude nezindlu.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Lithanda imozulu efudumeleyo, ukusuka kwi-10°C ukuya kwi-35°C.

Likhula kakuhle kwiindawo ezinemvula encinci.

Lithanda ukukhula elangeni ngokupheleleyo kodwa liyakwazi ukumelana nokukhanya okuphakathi.

Sisihlahlana esiqinileyo esinyamezelayo kwimimoya enomkhenkce, nakwiimeko zomhlaba ezomileyo neziphantse zomile.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Likholisa ukukhula kakuhle kulo naluphi na uhlobo lomhlaba oxubileyo kwaye okhulula amanzi kakuhle.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Likhula lula ngama-cuttings anyangwe ngezinto ezikhuthaza iingcambu, kuba imbewu ayixhaphakanga.

Ama-cuttings okanye ama-truncheons akhula iingcambu ngokulula, kwaye oku kwenzeka phakathi kweeveki ezi-4 nezi-6.

Izithole zifuna amanzi amancinci kakhulu.

Lakuba lizinzile, likhula ngokukhawuleza kwaye lifikelela ekuvuthweni phakathi kweminyaka emi-2 ne-5.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/portulacaria-afra>

Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes,
Wikimedia Commons

IKHAMANGA YASE NATAL

Strelitzia nicolai (L), Natal wild banana (E), skamanga, ikhamanga (X)

Lo mthi ufumaneka kunxweme olusempuma ye-Afrika eseMazantsi kwaye ukhula kwindawo yehlathi elingunaphakade kunye nehlathi lemithombo yolwandle.

Iziqhamo zikhula njengeepod ezomeleleyo, ebusika nasekwinda. Imbewu engavuthwanga iyatyiswa kwaye imnandi, kodwa mayityiwe kancinci.

Lo mthi uneentonga ezininzi kwaye ukhula ube ziimitha ezi-7 ubude, ngamagqabi amakhulu amise okwefan.

Ufanelekile ukuba utyalwe kufutshane nemigca yamandla, iindlela zikawonke-wonke, kodwa kufuneka kude nemibhobho yamanzi kunye nezakhiwo ngenxa yeengcambu zawo ezinamandla kakhulu.

IXESHA LOKUTYALA			
Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
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Sep	Oct	Nov	

IMPILO NOKUTYA

Iipod zeziqhamo azityiwa, kodwa imbewu engavuthwanga ingagaywa ibe ngumgubo, ixutywe namanzi ize iphekwe njenje fritter.

Imbewu inobutyebi befayibha yendalo, eluncedo kwimpilo yesisu nokugaya ukutya.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Iingalo zamagqabi zomiswa zisetyenziswe ukwenza imitya yezikhuselo zeentlanzi kunye neehuts.

Xa ityalwe ininzi elandelelanayo, ingenza umqobo oxhathisayo emoyeni.

Lo mthi mkhulu ungatyalwa njengomthi wokuhombisa ngenxa yamagqabi awo amakhulu kunye neentyatyambo ezikhethekileyo.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Iintyatyambo ezimangalisayo zitsala iimpukane, iinyosi, namabhabhathane.

Imithi exineneyo esezantsi komthi inika indawo yokuhlala amasele, amadada, neentaka.

Eminye imibungu njengamaqonya yenza uthungelwano lwesilika phakathi kwamagqabi.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/strelitzia-nicolai>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

IKHAMANGA YASE NATAL

Strelitzia nicolai (L), Natal wild banana (E), skamanga, ikhamanga (X)

Lo mthi ungowemveli kunxweme olusempuma ye-Afrika eseMazantsi kwaye ufumaneka kwindawo yelathi le-Indian Ocean Coastal Belt.

Izinambuzane zitya kwaye zihlala phakathi kwamagqabi, iinkawu, iintaka, kunye ne-blue duiker zidla iintyatyambo, iintaka kunye neenkawu zitya imbewu okanye iziqhamo.

Ukusasazwa kwenziwa ziintaka, ngakumbi ii-sunbirds. Lo mthi usasazeka kakhulu ngeengcambu ezihluma kumthi omkhulu.

Njengoko utsala iintaka ezininzi, izinambuzane, nezilwanyana, kungcono ukuwutyala kwiindawo ezivulekileyo, kude nezakhiwo.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

Dec	Jan	Feb	
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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Lo mthi uthanda ubushushu obuphakathi kwe-18°C ne-29°C.

Ukukhula kwawo kulungile kwiindawo ezinemvula eninzi.

Ufuna ukukhula kwindawo enelanga ngokupheleleyo.

Lo mthi uqhuba kakuhle nokuba kusebusika kwaye uyanyamezela imozulu enomkhenkce.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Lo mthi unokukhula kwiindidi ezahlukeneyo zomhlaba ezikhupha amanzi kakuhle.

Uthanda ukukhula kumhlaba one-pH epakathi kwe-6 ne-7.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Eyona ndlela isebenzayo yokuwutyala kukuthatha iingcambu ezihluma kumthi omkhulu unyaka wonke.

Ukukhulisa umthi ukusuka kwimbewu, kufuneka ususe inyama eyogqume imbewu, uwuutywilisele emanzini ubusuku bonke phambi kokutyala.

Izithole zifuna ukufakelwa amanzi rhoqo.

Lo mthi ukhula ngokukhawuleza kwaye ufikelela ekuvuthweni kwiminyaka emi-4 phantsi kweemeko zokukhula ezifanelekileyo.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/strelitzia-nicolai>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

ILALANYATHI / UMNQABAZA

Grewia occidentalis (L), cross-berry (E), ilalanyathi, umnqabaza (X)

Lo mthi ufunyanwa eMzantsi Afrika uphela, ngakumbi kunxweme olusempuma, kwaye ukhula kwiindawo, ukusuka eKaroo, kumahlathi aselunxwemeni, kumahlathi ahlala eluhlaza asezingtabeni, nase-savanna-bushveld, ukuya kubude obuyi-2,500m.

Iziqhamo ezinamalobhu amane, eziyi-1cm ubukhulu, kwaye ziveliswa kwiindidi ukusuka ngoJanuwari ukuya kuMeyi. Zinokutyiwa ziluhlaza, zibe yijusi okanye zenziwe ijam.

Ukhula njengomthi osisihlahla okanye omncinci kwaye ungafikelela kwi-3m phantsi. Ngokunenkqubo yeengcambu ephakathi, ukuwa kwezityalo kunye neziqhamo eziphantsi, esi sityalo sifanelekile ekutyalweni kufutshane nezakhiwo, iindlela, imibhobho yamanzi, kunye neengcingo zombane.

IXESHA LOKUQHAMBA				
Dec	Jan	Feb	☀️	
Mar	Apr	May	🌿	
Jun	Jul	Aug	❄️	
Sep	Oct	Nov	🌸	

IMPILO NOKUTYA

Iziqhamo ziqulethe iivithamini A, B, no-C, ezibalulekileyo kwimpilo yomzimba, amandla, kunye nokomeleza amasosha omzimba.

Utyebile ngekalhsiyam, intsimbi, ipotasiyam kunye ne-zinc, ezinceda ekomelezeni igazi, amathambo kunye nezihlunu.

Iziqulatho ze-amino acids ezifunwa ziiseli (cells) zomzimba ukuze zisebenze kakuhle.

Ixolo lithi xa licwiliswe emanzini ashushu, lisetyenziselwe ukunyangama amanxeba okanye izilonda.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Amagqabi adliwa ziinkomo, iibhokhwe, kunye nezinye izilwanyana zasekhaya.

Xa utyalwe ngomgca, wenza uthango oluzinzileyo.

Umthi usetyenziswa ekwenzeni iintsika zocingo kunye nezixhobo.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Esi sityalo sitsala iinyosi kunye neebhabhathane, ezibalulekileyo ekwandiseni ukukhula kwezityalo.

Amagqabi adliwa ziinyamakazi, iindlelamthi, kunye ne-grey duiker.

Esi sityalo sinokumelana nobusika obubandayo kunye nexesha lendlala.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/grewia-occidentalis>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist

ILALANYATHI / UMNQABAZA

Grewia occidentalis (L), bow-wood, cross-berry, star-flower (E), ilalanyathi, umnqabaza (X)

Isihlahla sivala kumbindi weAfrika kwaye sifumaneka kwi-Albany thicket, fynbos, iingca ezinde okanye emadlelweni, unxweme lwaselwandlekazi i-Indian ocean, Nama Karoo, savanna, kunye neSucculent Karoo biomes.

Iintyatyambo zawo zityebile nge-nectar, etsala izinambuzane. Amagqabi athandwa yimibungu yeebhathathane, ibhokhwe, rhino, ndlulamthi, nyala ne-grey duiker. Iziqhamo ezivuthileyo zithandwa ziintaka kunye nezinye izilwanyana.

Iintyatyambo zisasazwa, zithwalwe zizinambuzane, kwaye imbewu isasazwa ziintaka kunye nezinye izilwanyana. Ivelisa imbewu eninzi, ehluma lula, nto leyo enokwenza izithole ezininzi zikhule kufutshane nomthi omdala.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Isihlahla sikwazi ukumelana neemeko ezininzi zemozulu, kodwa sikhula kakuhle kumaqondo obushushu aphakathi kwe-20°C ne-38°C.

Sikhula kwiindawo zemvula epezulu kodwa sikwakwazi ukumelana nexesha lesomiso.

Siyakwazi ukukhula elangeni ngokupheleleyo okanye kwiindawo enethunzi elincinci.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Sikhula kakuhle kwiindidi ezahlukeneyo zomhlaba, kuquka isanti, umhlaba ophakathi, kunye nodongwe olunzima.

Singamkela umhlaba onepH etshintshela phakathi kwe-asidi, neutral, kunye ne-alkaline.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Imbewu entsha kufuneka icwiliswe emanzini ubusuku bonke phambi kokuhlwayelwa ukususela ngolanuwari ukuya ku-Aprili.

Imbewu ihluma lula phakathi kweeveki ezi-2 ukuya kwezi-6.

Ingakhuliswa nakumasebe asikiweyo afakwe ihomoni, ehlotyeni nasekwindla.

Izityalo ezisencinci zifuna amanzi amaninzi ukuze zikhule kakuhle.

Sikhula ngokukhawuleza ekuqaleni kodwa sicotha xa sisiba sidala.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/grewia-occidentalis>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist

ISUNDU

Phoenix reclinata (L), wild date palm (E), isundu (X)

Isundu lifumaneka kulo lonke eMzantsi Afrika, likhula kufutshane nemilambo nakwiindawo ezinamanzi, lindonga zemilambo nemigxobhozo ezinamathafa aphezulu anamanzi, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-3,000m.

Iziqhamo zikhula ngobuninzi zenza amaqela, obungange-2.5cm, kwaye zivuthwa phakathi kukaFebruwari noAprili. Zinokutyiwa ziluhlaza okanye zenziwe ijusi.

Umthi ukhula ukuya kubude obungange-5m kunye nomqhele obanzi.

Ngenxa yokuba awunazimpande ezinzulu kakhulu kunye neenkunkuma zamagqabi ezingagqithisiyo, umthi ungalinywa kufutshane nezindlu, iindlela, kunye neengcingo zombane, kodwa makungalinywa kufutshane nemibhobho yamanzi ngenxa yokukhula kakhulu kweziqhamo.

IXESHA LOKUQHAMBA				
Dec	Jan	Feb	☀️	
Mar	Apr	May	🌿	
Jun	Jul	Aug	❄️	
Sep	Oct	Nov	🌸	

IMPILO NOKUTYA

- Iziqhamo ziqulathe iivithamini A, B, kunye no-C eziphucula impilo kunye nenkqubo yokuzikhusela emzimbeni.
- Zine-calcium, iron, magnesium, kunye ne-phosphorus eziqinisa amathambo, igazi kunye nezihlunu.
- Zizele ngama-amino acids abalulekileyo ekusebenzeni kweeseli (cells) zomzimba.
- Iziqhamo zivelisa ubisi olusetyenziswa ekwenzeni iziselo ezinxilisayo.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

- Le palm inika ithunzi elininzi kwaye ungalinywa njengomqobo womoya.
- Ifibre zamagqabi ziyasetyenziswa ukwenza izitya, imitshayelo, iminqwazi, kunye neengcango.
- Amagqabi ayo asetyenziswa ukwenza izinxibo ezinxitywa ngamadodana amaXhosa ngexesha lomgidi wabo wokwaluka.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

- Ungasetyenziswa njengenqaba ephilayo yokuthintela izilwanyana zasemakhaya.
- Esi sityalo siqinileyo sinokumelana nomkhenkce, nokuhlala emanzini, kwaye siyakwazi ukumelana nokunqongophala kwamanzi.
- Umthi unceda ukomeleza umhlaba kunye nokuthintela ukhukuliseko lwemilambo.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/phoenix-reclinata>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist

ISUNDU

Phoenix reclinata (L), wild date palm (E), isundu (X)

Lo mthi uvela kunxweme olusempuma yoMzantsi Afrika kwaye ufumaneka kwindawo ye-savanna.

Amabungu amabhabhathane atya amagqabi, logama izilwanyana ezifana neenkawu neenkamela zidla iziqhamo.

Iintyatyambo zipollinethwa zizinambuzane, kwaye iintaka nezilwanyana zihambisa imbewu yawo.

Lo mthi ungowamadoda nowasetyhini (dioecious), ngoko ke kufuneka utyalwe ngokwamaqela ukuze kukhutjizwe ukwandiseka kwawo.

Ngenxa yokuba uyasasazeka, kufuneka ufumanise indawo evulekileyo eninzi ukuze ukhule ngokupheleleyo.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uzizwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

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IMEKO YOKUKHULA

Lo mthi uthanda indawo efudumeleyo kwaye unokumelana neendidi zobushushu ukusuka kwi-15°C ukuya kwi-35°C.

Ukhula kakuhle kwiindawo ezifumana imvula ephakathi ukuya kwephezulu, phakathi kwe-500mm ne-1,500mm ngonyaka.

Uthanda ukukhanya kwelanga okanye ukuhlala kwisithunzi esincinci, kodwa awuzukuhluma iziqhamo ukuba ukhuliswe kwisithunzi esingaphezulu.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Ungakwazi ukumelana nokuhlala emanzini, ukufuma okuphantsi kunye nomhlaba ongaphucukanga kakhulu.

Ukhula kakuhle kumhlaba one-pH ephakathi kwe-5 ne-7.5.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Umthi ungalinywa usebenzisa imbewu ecocekileyo.

Imbewu ihluma phakathi kweeveki ezi-8 ne-12.

Amasebe (suckers) anokuthathwa emithini emidla.

Izityalo ezisencinci kufuneka zifumane amanzi aneleyo.

Umthi ukhula ngokuphakathi kwaye ufikelela ekukhuleni ngokupheleleyo emva kweminyaka emihlanu.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/phoenix-reclinata>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist

LALA PALM

Hyphaene coriacea (L), lala palm, ilala palm, gingerbread tree, fan palm (E), ilala (X)

Ilala lifumaneka kunxweme olusempuma lweMzantsi Afrika, ingakumbi kufutshane nemilambo, kwiingxangxasi zesanti nakwiindunduma zolwandle.

Iziqhamo ezimalunga ne-5cm ziveliswa ngamaqela unyaka wonke. Zithatha iminyaka emibini ukuze zivuthwe kwaye zingasetyenziswa ukwenza ubisi okanye ijusi.

Likhula libe ngumthi omalunga ne-5m oneziqhu ezininzi kunye namagqabi amakhulu aqinileyo. Zonke iinxalenye zesi siqu ziyasetyenziswa, nto leyo eyenza sibe sisityalo esinokusetyenziswa ngeendlela ezininzi.

Ingcambu yaso ayingeni nzulu kakhulu, kwaye ngenxa yokuphakama kwayo okuphakathi nendawo kunye namagqabi angawi ngobuninzi emhlabeni, isityalo silungele ukutyalwa kufutshane nezakhiwo, imibhobho yamanzi, imigca yamandla kunye neendlela.

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Ilala liyimithombo etyebileyo yeevithamini B no-C, eziluncedo empilweni yengqondo, igazi kunye nokomeleza amajoni omzimba.

Inyama yesiqhamo isetyenziselwa ukunyanga iingxaki zesisu nokucoca amathumbu.

Amagqabi aselula anokutyiwa njengemifino.

Kunento elingaphakathi kwegqabi eliphezulu ikhutshelwa ubisi kwaye ingavundiswa ukuze kwenziwe isiselo esinxilisayo.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Amagqabi esityalo asetyenziswa njengesondlo kwizilwanyana ezifuywayo.

Umthi usetyenziselwa ukwenza iintsika zokuthintela, izixhobo neenkuni zomlilo.

Ifayibha evela kumagqabi isetyenziswa ekwalukeni mabhakede kunye neengxowa.

Imbewu ifana ne-ivory yezityalo.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Iziqhamo zingumthombo wokutya weendlovu kunye neemfene.

Iziseko zamagqabi amadala avulekileyo zinika iintaka indawo yokwakha indlwane zokuzalela.

Siyanceda ekumiliseni umhlaba nasekuthinteleni ukhukhuluseko lomhlaba.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/hyphaene-coriacea>
 Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

LALA PALM

Hyphaene coriacea (L), lala palm, ilala palm, gingerbread tree, fan palm (E), ilala (X)

Ilala livela kunxweme olusempuma lweMzantsi Afrika kwaye lidla ngokufumaneka kummandla wonxweme woLwandlekazi lwase i-Indian ocean nakwi-savanna biomes.

Iindlovu neemfene zitya iziqhamo, logama iintaka zifumana indawo yokuhlala kumagqabi.

Esisihlahla sinesini esingafaniyo, oko kuthetha ukuba isityalo ngasinye siveza iintyatyambo zodwa zomfazi okanye ezendoda. Kufuneka kutyalwe imithi emininzi kunye ukuze kukhuthazwe ukuveliswa kweziqhamo.

Iintyatyambo zipollinated ngezinambuzane, kwaye imbewu isasazwa zizilwanyana.

Ngenxa yokuba itsala izinambuzane nezilwanyana, kungcono ukuyityala kude nezindlu.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Ikhula kwiindawo ezomileyo nezinobushushu, apho ubushushu buphakathi kwe-10°C nangaphezulu.

Inganyamezela imvula ephakathi kwe-250mm kunye ne-1,500mm ngonyaka.

Umthi uthanda ukutyalwa elangeni elipheleleyo.

Lo mthi unganyamezela ukoma kwaye awulahlali amagqabi unyaka wonke.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Ikhula kwimihlaba yesanti enomlambo kunye nomhlaba onodongwe, isanti kunye nowothuli.

Ikhetha umhlaba onepH enobukrwada obungaphezulu kwe-7 (alkaline).

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Iziqhamo kufuneka ziqhekeke ukuze imbewu ikhutshwe phambi kokutyala.

Imbewu etyalwa entwasahlobo, phakathi nehlobo okanye ekwindla, idla ngokuhluma phakathi kweentsuku eziyi-14 ukuya kwi-180.

Amaxolo okanye izithole zinokuthatyathwa kwisityalo esikhulu ukuze kutyalwe entsha.

Izityalo eziselula kunye nezithole zifuna ukuniselwa kakuhle.

Zikhula kancinci, kwaye ngonyaka zivelisa igqabi elitsha elinye kuphela.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/hyphaene-coriacea>
 Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

UMBHONGISA

Diospyros lycioides (L), star-apple, bluebush, monkey plum (E), umbhongisa (X)

Umbhongisa ufumaneka kulo lonke elaseMzantsi Afrika, kufutshane nemilambo, emahlathini nasezindulini ukuya kubude obuyi-1,000m.

Iziqhamo ezincinci, malunga ne-2cm ubukhulu, kwaye ziveliswa ukusuka ngoJanuwari ukuya kuJuni, zityiwa ziluhlaza, zifakwe kwijusi, okanye zenziwe ijam.

Isityalo sikhula sibe sisihlahla okanye umthi omncinci esiphakathi, esifikelela kubude obuyi-3m.

Ukuphakama kwaso okuphakathi nendawo, amasebe ebanzi kodwa engachithi amagqabi amaninzi, kunye nenkqubo yeengcambu ezinganweniyo, kwenza kube ukutyalwa kufutshane nemigca yombane, imibhobho yamanzi, iindlela kunye nezindlu.

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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Ziqulethe amanqwawqwa amaninzi eevithamini A no-C, eziphindwe kabini kunezo zeorenji, ukuxhasa impilo yeeseli kunye nokukhusela amajoni omzimba.

Ziqulethe i-calcium, i-phosphorus kunye ne-iron ezixhasa impilo yamathambo, imisipha, kunye negazi.

Iziqhamo zisetyenziswa ekwenzeni utywala obufana ne-bhiya, kwaye imbewu yazo inokuthatha indawo yekofu.

Iingcambu ziyahlafunwa ukunyanga imikhuhlane kunye nokhohlokhohlo.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Esi sihlahla sixatyisiwe njengehlathi lokubonelela ngomthunzi kunye nokhuseleko kumoya.

Umthi wawo usetyenziselwa ukwenza izibonda zokubiya, izipuni, izinto zokudlala, izixhobo zokwakha, kunye nefenitshala.

Umbala ophuzi-brown ukhutshelwa kwiingcambu zawo, kwaye ulusu/ixolo lwawo luyasetyenziswa ekulungiseni ulusu okanye isikhumba.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Isityalo sisetyenziswa kakhulu ziinyosi njengomthombo wonyibilikisi weentyatyambo, kwaye iziqhamo zityiwa ziintaka.

Isihlahla esityebileyo sivelisa indawo yokuhlala yezilwanyana ezincinci.

Esi sihlahla sikhala ixesha elide, sinokumelana nexesha lokomisa kwaye asifuni manzi amaninzi.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/diospyros-lycioides>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist,
 Wikimedia Commons

UMBHONGISA

Diospyros lycioides (L), star-apple, bluebush (E), umbhongiisa (X)

Esi sityalo sivela eMazantsi e-Afrika kwaye sixhaphake kwiindidi ezahlukeneyo ezifana ne-Albany thicket, i-fynbos, intlango ye-savanna, i-Indian Ocean coastal belt, kunye neKaroo.

Sidlala indima ebalulekileyo ekuxhaseni intsingiselo yobomi ngokubonelela ngokutya kwezinzambuzane, iintaka, oodassie kunye neenkawu.

Esi sihlahla sibizwa ngokuba yi-dioecious, oko kuthetha ukuba isityalo ngasinye sivelisa kuphela iintyatyambo zesini esinye—ezokuba yindoda okanye umfazi—ngoko sithembele kwizinzambuzane ukusasaza iintyatyambo zaso.

Kungcono ukutyala izityalo ezininzi kunye ukuze zivelise iziqhamo ngokwaneleyo.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

- Isityalo sifaneleke kwimozulu efudumeleyo kunye nephakathi, ukusuka kwi-10°C ukuya kwi-35°C.
- Sifaneleke kwiindawo ezinemvula ephakathi unyaka wonke.
- Sithanda ukukhanya kwelanga ngokupheleleyo kwaye sinokumelana nexesha lesomiso.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

- Sikhula kwimihlaba eyahlukeneyo enokuphumela kakuhle amanzi.
- Limeko ezifanelekileyo zifuna i-pH ephakathi kwe-4 ne-7.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

- Imbewu ifanele icwiliswe emanzini ashushu ubusuku bonke phambi kokutyala.
- Iya kuhluma phakathi kweentsuku eziyi-18 ukuya kweziyi-20.
- Isihlahla sifuna amanzi aphaqathi ukuze sikhule kakuhle.
- Ukususa imiphezulu yamasebe asakulayo kuya kukhuthaza ukukhula okuqinisekileyo nokubanzi.
- Esi sityalo sikhula kancinci kwaye siza kufikelela kubudala obufanelekileyo emva kweminyaka emine.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/diospyros-lycioides>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist,
 Wikimedia Commons

UMBINZA

Halleria lucida (L), tree fuchsia, white olive (E), umbinza (X)

Umbinza ufumaneka kulo lonke elaseMazantsi e-Afrika, ngakumbi kwiindawo ezinehlathi, emifuleni, kwiindawo ezinamawa, kwiinduli, nasecaleni kwamanzi.

Umthi uvelisa iziqhamo ezibumbeneyo i-10mm ngobukhulu, eziveliswa ngamaqela. Zityiwa yintaka ngakumbi kuba azinambitheki kakhulu ebantwini.

Lo mthi uhlala uluhlaza unyaka wonke kwaye ungakhula ukusuka kwi-5m ukuya kwi-10m, ube namasebe ajonge phantsi kunye ne canopy etyebileyo esasazekayo.

Inkqubo yeengcambu ezingekho ndlongondlongo, amagqabi angachithwa kakhulu, kunye neziqhamo ezingekho zininzi kakhulu kwenza lo mthi ulungele ukutyalwa kufutshane nezakhiwo, imibhobho yamanzi, kunye neendlela.

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IMPILO NOKUTYA

- Iziqhamo ziqulethe i-phosphorus, ebalulekileyo ekwakhiweni kwamathambo, amazinyo, kunye neeseli zomzimba.
- Zine-amino acids, ezibalulekileyo kwiiseli zomzimba ukuze zisebenze kakuhle.
- Intsalela okanye izinto ezifunyanwa kulo mthi zisetyenziswa ukwenza amayeza okwelaph iindlebe nezinye iintlungu zomzimba.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

- Iintyatyambo neziqhamo zakha umtsalane ohlukeneyo weentaka egadini.
- Umthi unokusetyenziswa njengomthombo weenkuni zomlilo, kunye nokwenza izibonda zokubiyela kunye nezixhobo ezincinci.
- Ungatyalwa njengesithinteli somoya kwaye uvelisa umthunzi omhle.

UKUNCEDA KWIINDALO

- Iintyatyambo ezityebileyo kwi-nectar zitsala izinambuzane ezithwala intyantyambo, kunye neentaka.
- Amagqabi atyiwa yimfuyo yasekhaya kunye nezilwanyana eziphila endle.
- Lo mthi awufuni nkathalelo ininzi, ulukhuni, kwaye umelana nemozulu eyomileyo kunye nobusika obubandayo.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/halleria-lucida>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes

UMBINZA

Halleria lucida (L), tree fuchsia, white olive (E), umbinza (X)

Esi sityalo sivela eMazantsi e-Afrika kwaye sixhaphake kwiindidi ezifana ne-Albany thicket, fynbos, intlangonye-savanna, i-Indian Ocean coastal belt, Nama Karoo kunye ne-Succulent Karoo.

Sisityalo esibalulekileyo kwindalo, kuba sinceda ekutsaleni iinyosi, iintaka, kunye nezinye izinambuzane eziphilayo. Iziqhamo zityiwa ziintaka, kwaye amagqabi adliwa zizilwanyana eziphila kwindalo.

Iintyatyambo zithwalwa ziinyosi, kwaye imbewu yaso isasazwa ziintaka ezitya iziqhamo.

Njengoko itsala iinyosi ezininzi, iintaka, kunye nezinambuzane, kungcono sityalwe kude nezindlu.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Lo mthi umelana nothotho lwamazinga obushushu, ukusuka kwi-10°C ukuya kwi-35°C.

Uyathanda ukufumana amanzi apheleleyo, kodwa unokumelana namaxesha omileyo.

Ukukhula kakuhle, uthanda ukukhanya kwelanga, kodwa uyayithanda nesemi-shade.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Uyathanda umhlaba one-sandy loam, kodwa unokunyamezela neminye imihlaba enokuhlaza kakuhle amanzi.

Uyathanda i-pH ephakathi kwe-6 ne-7, phakathi kwe-asidi kunye nenkqubo engathathi cala.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Imbewu inokuhlwayelwa ukusuka ngoSeptemba ukuya kuDisemba, okanye ngoMatshi ukuya kuMeyi.

Inokukhuliswa ngokusikwa kusetyenziswe irooting hormone ukukhuthaza ukukhula, emva koko zifakwe kwindawo efumileyo ephakathi kwenkungu ethile.

Imbewu ihluma phakathi kweeveki eziyi-2 ukuya kweziyi-6.

Izityalo ezintsha zifuna amanzi apheleleyo.

Umthi ukhula ngokukhawuleza kwaye ufikelela ebudaleni kwiinyanga ezingama-24 (iminyaka emibini).

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/halleria-lucida>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes

UMDUBU

Combretum erythrophyllum (L), river bushwillow (E), umdubu (X)

Umdubu ufumaneka eMzantsi Afrika, kwiindawo ezinehlathi elomileyo okanye i-savanna, ngakumbi emilanjani, ukuya kuma-1,500m ngaphezu kolwandle.

Imbewu yayo eyi-1-1,5cm inetyhefu kwaye iveliswa ngamakhama okanye ngamaqela ehlotyeni, kwaye isetyenziswa ukwenza i-dye. Imbewu yayo eyodwa enamaphiko amane ihlala emthini ixesha elide, yonyusa umtsalane wayo njengomthi wokuhombisa.

Lo mthi ukhula ngokukhawuleza, ukuya kubude obuyi-5m, kwaye unecanopy ephakathi.

Ubude obuphakathi, ukunaba okulinganiselweyo, amazinga aphantsi okunwenwa kweengcambu namagqabi awayo amalwa, kuyenza ilungele ukutyalwa kufutshane nezakhiwo, iindlela, imigca yamanzi nombane.

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Imbewu kunye neengcambu zomthi zithathwa njengezinyetyhefu, kodwa ngamanye amaxesha zisetyenziswa njengeyeza lokucoca umzimba kunye nonyango lwezifo ezithathelana ngesondo.

Kufuneka kuqatshelwe xa kusetyenziswa lo mthi kwiinjongo zonyango, njengoko unetyhefu kwaye unokubangela iihccups.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Umphunga omnyama ukhutshelwa kwiingcambu zawo, kwaye usetyenziswa ukwenza i-dye kushishino lokunyangwa iinwele.

linkuni zomthi zisetyenziswa kulwakhiwo, ukwenza iintonga, iintsika zocingo kunye nezixhobo.

Ubume bawo obuhle, ixolo elinomtsalane kunye namagqabi atshintsha umbala ehlotyeni, kuyenza ibe ngumthi othandwayo wokuhombisa ononcedo kwindalo.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Iintyatyambo zitsala ii-wasps, kwaye imbewu yayo idliwa ziintaka.

Umthi ukhula ngokukhawuleza, unika umthunzi, ukhuseleko kwaye unokutyalwa njengesithinteli somoya.

Lo mthi ulungele imeko ezahlukeneyo, awufuni nkathalelo eninzi ekukhuleni, awufuni manzi amaninzi, kwaye uyaxhathisa kwiimeko zokoma.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:

<https://pza.sanbi.org/combretum-erythrophyllum>

Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, iSpotnature

UMDUBU

Combretum erythrophyllum (L), river bushwillow (E), umdubu (X)

Lo mthi uvela eMzantsi Afrika kwaye uqhele ukufumaneka kwimimandla ye-Albany thicket, Indian Ocean coastal belt kunye ne-savanna biomes.

Unegalelo eliphakathi kwi-biodiversity, njengoko ii-wasps kunye neentaka zitya iziqhamo zawo, ngelixa amagqabi edliwa ziindlulamthi neendlovu.

Ukuthuthwa kothuli lweentyatyambo kwenziwa ikakhulu ngama-wasps, athi ngamanye amaxesha abeke amaqanda awo kwimbewu yomthi.

Lo mthi uvelisa imbewu eninzi enokuhluma ngokulula, kwaye unokufumanisa izithole ezincinci zingqonge umthi omdala.

Ngenxa yokuba lo mthi unomtsalane kuma-wasps, kufanelekile ukuwutyala kude nekhaya.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Lo mthi unokumelana neentlobo ngeentlobo zeemeko zemozulu, kodwa uthanda ubushushu phakathi kwe-10°C - 35°C.

Ufuna imvula ephakathi ngonyaka ukuze ukhule kakuhle.

Uthanda ukutyalwa phantsi kwelanga elipheleleyo, kodwa unokunyamezela indawo enethunzi elincinane.

Uyaxhathisa kwimozulu eyomileyo nakubusika: "flexy is sexy"!

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Lo mthi unokukhula kwiintlobo ezahlukeneyo zomhlaba - i-loam, isanti kunye nodongwe.

Iimeko ezifanelekileyo zokukhula zifuna i-pH ephakathi kwe-5 ne-7.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Ingakhuliswa kwimbewu entsha ekufuneka icwiliswe emanzini ubusuku bonke phambi kokutyala.

Imbewu ihluma phakathi kweentsuku ezi-7 nezi-14.

Qinisekisa ukuba izithole kunye nezityalo ezincinci zigcinwa zizanzi, kodwa zingafumani manzi angaphezulu.

Lo mthi ukhula ngokukhawuleza kwaye unokufikelela ebudaleni kwawo emva kweminyaka.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/combretum-erythrophyllum>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, iSpotnature

UMGADANKAWU / UMHLANDLOTHI

Albizia adianthifolia (L), Flat crown (E), umgadankawu, umhlandlothi (X)

Lo mthi uyafumaneka kwiindawo ezishushu nakumantla eMzantsi Afrika, kumahlathi asezingtabeni nasemazantsi, kwimida yamahlathi, kumahlathi avulekileyo nasezintilini eziphakathi kwama-250m nama-450m.

Iziqhamo zalo mthi azidliwa, kodwa imbewu equlethwe kwiingqolowa zingatshintshwa zibe lusosi.

Lo mthi ukhula ngokukhawuleza kwaye unokufikelela kubude ne-10m. Unomthunzi omkhulu, awufanelanga ukutyalwa kufutshane nemigca yamandla ombane.

Iingcambu zawo azinamandla kakhulu, kwaye iintyatyambo zawo azivelisi inkunkuma eninzi, nto leyo eyenza ukuba ulungele ukutyalwa kufuphi nemibhobho yamanzi kunye nezakhiwo.

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Umphunga owenziwa kwixolo usetyenziselwa ukunyanga izifo zesikhumba kunye nebronchitis.

Iingcambu zixutywa ukuze kusetyenziselwe ukunyanga amehlo avuthayo nezifo zesikhumba.

Ixolo lisetyenziswa ekunyangeni iintsholongwane zangaphakathi kunye neetapeworms.

Ixolo elifakwe umgubo lisetyenziselwa ukunyanga intloko ezibuhlungu nesayinasitis.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Lo mthi uneqokobhe elibanzi nelisasazekileyo, nto leyo eyenza kube ngumthi womthunzi, isithinteli moya.

Ngenxa yokuma kwawo, lo mthi uyathandwa njengomthi wokuhlobisa.

Umthi lo uluncedo kwizakhiwo, ukhuni lwaso lusetyenziselwa ukwakha, ukwenza izinto zobugcisa kunye nokutsha njengamafutha omlilo.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Lo mthi ubalulekile kwindalo, njengoko utsala izinambuzane ezilungileyo, utyiwa yimibungu okanye amaqonya.

Iingcambu zawo zinceda ukutyebisa umhlaba ngokufaka initrogen.

Usetyenziselwa ukulawula ukhukuliseko lomhlaba.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/albizia-adianthifolia-var-adianthifolia>

Imifanekiso: PlantZAfrica, Wikimedia

UMGADANKAWU / UMHLANDLOTHI

Albizia adianthifolia (L), Flat crown (E), umgadankawu, umhlandlothi (X)

Lo mthi usuka kumantla eMzantsi Afrika, kwaye ufumaneka kumabhanti aselunxwemeni lwe Indian Ocean noluhlaza lwesavanna.

Iintyatyambo zawo zivela ngobuninzi kwaye utsala izinambuzane ezithanda incindi, usisondlo kwizibungu (butterfly larvae).

Imbewu entsha ingagcinwa iinyanga ezi-3 ngaphambi kokutyala.

Ngenxa yokutsala izinambuzane, kuyacetyiswa ukuba ungatyalali kufuphi nezakhiwo zabantu.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Ubushushu obufanelekileyo bokukhula: kwe-22°C ne-28°C, kodwa bunganyamezela kwe-15°C ne-34°C.

Ukhula kakuhle kwiindawo ezinemvula eninzi, phakathi kwe-1,500mm ne-2,500mm, kodwa unganyamezela kwe-900mm ne-4,000mm.

Uthanda ukukhula elangeni kwaye akanyamezeli iqabaka.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Umthi lo ukhula kakuhle emhlabeni ochumileyo.

Kufuneka umhlaba ube kwizinga le-pH phakathi kwe-4 ukuya kwi-7.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Imbewu mayigalelwe emanzini ashushu ubusuku bonke phambi kokutyala.

Imbewu mayifakwe emigqomeni emikhulu okanye ityalwe ngokuthe ngqo emhlabeni xa inamagqabi amabini.

Iimbewu kunye nemithi emincinci mayifakwe amanzi rhoqo.

Ukukhula kungaphakathi kwe 1m – 2m nkonyaka phantsi kweemeko ezifanelekileyo.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/albizia-adianthifolia-var-adianthifolia>
 Imifanekiso: PlantZAfrica, Wikimedia

UMGWENYA

Harpephyllum caffrum (L), wild plum (E), umgwenya (X)

Lo mthi ufumaneka kwiindawo ezisempuma yeMzantsi Afrika, ngakumbi kumahlathi asembindini wemilambo, ukuya kuma-1,400m.

Iziqhamo ezimalunga ne-2.5cm ngobukhulu zivela ngamaqela amaninzi, ukusuka ngoMatshi ukuya kuJuni, kwaye zinokutyiwa zintsha, ukwenza ijusi okanye ziguqulwe zibe yijeli.

Umthi ungafikelela kubude obuyi-7m kwaye unecanopy ephakathi ngobukhulu.

Ngenxa yowiso oluqhelekileyo kwamagqabi kunye nengcambu ezingenzi umonakalo, ungatyalwa kufutshane nezakhiwo, iindlela, kunye nezinye izixhobo zophuhliso lwengingqi.

IXESHA LOKUQHAMBA

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

IMPILO NOKUTYA

Iziqhamo ziqulethe ivithamin C efanayo neyeorenji kunye nevitamin B, ezomeleza impilo kunye nokhuselo lomzimba.

Ziqulethe neentsalela zeeminerali ezinqabileyo nezingafumaneki lula kwezinye iziqhamo.

Isiselo esenziwe ngoqweqwe okanye ixolo lomthi sisetyenziswa kunyango lwesikhumba, izihlunu, kunye nezifo zamathambo kunyango lwemveli.

Uqweqwe okanye ixolo lomthi lusetyenziswa ekunyangeni i-acne ne-czema xa lusetyenziswa eluswini.

Uqweqwe olutshisiweyo oluphezulu luluncedo ekunyangeni ukwenzakala kwemisipha kunye nezitho ezaphukileyo.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Lo mthi unokukhula ube ngumthunzi obalulekileyo kwaye ungatyalwa njengothintelo lomoya.

Iinkuni zawo zisetyenziswa ekwenzeni izibonda zokubiyela, izixhobo, ifanitshala, kunye nezinto ezisetyenziselwa ukugrumba nokubaza.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Izilwanyana eziphila emadlelweni ezifana ne buck, ibushbabies, kunye neenkawu zitya iziqhamo zawo zize zisasaze imbewu.

Lo mthi uyanceda ekubambeni umhlaba, ukuthintela ukhukuliseko.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/harpephyllum-caffrum>
 Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, PlantZAfrica,
 Wikimedia Commons

UMGWENYA

Harpephyllum caffrum (L), wild plum (E), umgwenya (X)

Umgwenya uvela kunxweme olusempuma yeMzantsi e-Afrika kwaye ufumaneka kwiindawo ezifana neAlbany thicket, emadlelweni, i-savanna, kunye ne-Indian Ocean coastal belt.

Iziqhamo zityiwa ziintaka, iibushbabies, iinkawu, iimfene kunye neebush buck. Amabhabhathane kunye nemibungu atya amagqabi.

Umthi uyahlukana ngokwesini (dioecious), oko kuthetha ukuba izityalo ezahlukeneyo zineentyatyambo zesini esahlukileyo. Ukutyala imithi emininzi kufutshane kuya kukhuthaza ukuveliswa kweziquhamo.

Iintyatyambo zisasazwa zizinambuzane, kanti imbewu isasazwa ziintaka nezilwanyana ezitya iziquhamo.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Umthi ukhula kakuhle kwimimandla enobushushu obuphakathi kunye ne-subtropical phakathi kwe-20°C ne-35°C.

Uthanda ukukhanya kwelanga ngokupheleleyo kodwa ungamelana nesithunzi esincinci.

Umthi awufanelekanga kwiindawo ezibandayo.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Lo mthi unokukhula kwiindidi ezahlukeneyo zomhlaba.

Umhlaba one-pH ephakathi nolungelelene kakuhle ungcono kakhulu ekukhuleni kwawo.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Imbewu kufuneka ifakwe emanzini ubusuku bonke emva koko igrunjwe kakuhle.

Imbewu ihluma ngokukhawuleza phakathi kweentsuku ezi-7 nezi-11.

Unokuzalana nentonga ezomisweyo kwindawo enethunzi ngaphambi kokutyala, kwaye zihluma ngokulula.

Umthi uthanda amanzi amaninzi ukuze ukhule kakuhle.

Ukhula ngokukhawuleza, ufikelela kubude obuyi-1.5m ngonyaka, kwaye ufikelela kubude obuyi-7m phakathi kweminyaka emi-2 ukuya kwemi-3.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziquhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/harpephyllum-caffrum>
 Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, PlantZAfrica,
 Wikimedia Commons

UMKHUHLU

Trichilia emetica (L), Natal mahogany (E), umkuhlu (X)

Lo mthi ufumaneka kumazwe aseMzantsi Afrika, ukhula kumahlathi ngasemlanjeni nasemathafeni, ukuya kwi-1,800m.

Iziqhamo zikhula ngamaqela, nganye enemilinganiselo ye-2cm, ukusuka ngoJanuwari ukuya kuMeyi. Ziqulethe imbewu ezintathu ukuya kwezintandathu ezogqunywe ngo-aril ebomvu, kwaye zityiwa ziphekiwe.

Lo mthi osesiphakathini ukuya ebukhulwini ufikelela kumda ophakathi kwe-2m.

Ubude bawo kunye iziqhamo ezininzi okunzima zenza ukuba ungafanelekanga kutyalo kufutshane nemigca yamandla kunye neendlela, kodwa unelungelo kutyalo kufutshane nemibhobho yamanzi kunye nezikolo.

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

IMPILO NOKUTYA

Lo mthi uqulethe i-calcium, i-iron, i-magnesium kunye nezinye izinto ezibalulekileyo ezingaqhelekanga xa kulandelelwa impilo.

Ibharkh okanye ixolo lomkuhlu isetyenziselwa ukunyanga i-pneumonia, i-epilepsy kunye ne-leprosy.

Isetyenziswa njengeyeza lokwegquma okanye ukucima ukunyanga izifo.

Iingcambu zisetyenziselwa ukunyanga izifo ezifana necolds, i-cirrhosis, isifo esixhaphakileyo sokuphuma kwegazi.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Lo mthi utyalwa ukwenza umthunzi kunye nesithintelo somoya.

Umthi okhule ngokupheleleyo uyanconywa kwimveliso yefenitshala.

Iwoodi isetyenziswa njengenkuni zomlilo kunye nokwenza iintsika zobiyo nezixhobo zokusebenza.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Lo mthi usetyenziselwa ukumisela umhlaba nasekuthinteleni ukhukhuliseko lomhlaba.

I-cake yeoli yembewu isetyenziswa njenge-fertilizer yemvelo.

Amagqabi ayindawo yokuhlala iintaka kunye namalulwane.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/trichilia-emetica>

Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

UMKHUHLU

Trichilia emetica (L), Natal mahogany (E), umkuhlu (X)

Lo mthi uvela eMzantsi Afrika kwaye udla ngokufumaneka kumphandle wesavanna biome.

Iziqhamo kunye nembewu zidliwa zinkawu kunye neentaka, kwaye amagqabi adliwa zizilwanyana.

Iintyatyambo zipollinated yiinyosi, iintaka, kunye nezinye izinambuzane. Imbewu isasazwa ziintaka nezilwanyana ezitya iziqhamo nembewu.

Ukuphindaphinda kwenziwa ngembewu kunye nezithole kwaye zingatyalwa unyaka wonke.

Qinisekisa ukutyala umthi kwiindawo ezivulekileyo, kude nendlu, njengoko itsala izinambuzane ezahlukeneyo kwaye nezilwanyana.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Lo mthi uthanda imozulu epholileyo ukuya kwephakathi, enobushushu obuphakathi kwe-18°C kunye ne-32°C.

Uthanda imvula yonyaka ephakathi kwe-600mm.

Ukukhula kakuhle kwawo kwenziwa elangeni elipheleleyo kodwa uyakwazi ukumelana nemithunzi ethile.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Ukhula kakuhle kumhlaba one-loam kunye nemihlaba ehamba amanzi kakuhle.

Ukhetha umhlaba onepH ephakathi kwe-5 ne-7 (neutral).

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Imbewu kufuneka ityalwe isentsha, hayi eyomileyo, ukuze ihlume ngokuphumelelayo.

Imbewu idla ngokuhluma phakathi kweentsuku eziyi-10 ukuya kweziyi-20.

Izithole eziphathiswe iihomoni zinokuthathwa kwiimithi ekhule ngokupheleleyo.

Umthi ufuna amanzi afaneleyo.

Umthi ukhula ngesantya esiphakathi kwe-1,5m ngonyaka kumacandelo aphezulu, kwaye ufikelela ekuphumeleleni emva kwe-6 iminyaka.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/trichilia-emetica>

Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

UMLOVULOVU / UMNOVUNOVU

Cordia caffra (L), septee tree, saucer-berry (E), umlovulovu, umnovunovu, umnofunofu (X)

Lo mthi ufumaneka kunxweme olusempuma lweMzantsi Afrika, kwiinduli ezinehlathi nakwiindawo zamahlathi aselunxwemeni. Uqheleke ngakumbi ngaphakathi ezweni, kwiindawo ezinehlathi elomileyo nakumda wamahlathi.

Nangona isiqhamo sawo esi-orange esiyi-1cm, esiveliswa ngamaxhama ehlotyeni, sidliwayo, lo mthi uxatyiswa ngakumbi ngenxa yeenzuzo zawo zonyango kunye neenkuni.

Lo mthi owomeleleyo ukhula ukuya kubude obumaphakathi obuyi-6m.

Ngenxa yokuba unomthunzi omncinci, ingcambu ephakathi nobude obulinganiselweyo, kulungele ukutyalwa kufutshane nezakhiwo, kwimizila yombane namanzi.

IXESHA LOKUQHAMBANA			
Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

IMPILO NOKUTYA

Isiqhamo salo mthi sinamanqanaba aphezulu e-potassium kuninzi lwezityalo zasendle ezityiwayo, uyanceda kwintlungu zemisipha kunye nempilo yentliziyo.

Iqulethe i-calcium, i-magnesium, kunye ne-iron ezixhasa imisipha, amathambo kunye neenkqubo zokutshintshiselana kwemichiza emzimbeni.

Amalungu omthi asetyenziswa kunyango lweentloko ezibuhlungu, umkhuhlane kunye nezilonda.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Iinkuni zomthi zisetyenziswa ukwenza iintsika zocingo kunye nezixhobo zokwakha, kwaye ingca yentliziyo yayo ebomvu-pinki yenza ifenitshala entle.

Ngenxa ye-bharkhi yawo ekhethekileyo, lo mthi uthandwa kakhulu njengomthi wokuhombisa onezibonelelo kwindalo.

Iingcongolo zomthi ezomileyo zisetyenziswa ukuqalisa umlilo.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Lo mthi utsala izinambuzane ezithutha uthuli lweentyatyambo kunye neentaka egadini.

Xa unqunyiwe kwaye ulungisiwe, ungasetyenziswa njengothango olomeleleyo okanye.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/cordia-caffra>

Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, PlantZAfrica,
Wikimedia Commons

UMLOVULOVU / UMNUNOVUNOVU

Cordia caffra (L), septe tree, saucer-berry (E), umlovulovu, umnovunovu, umnofunofu (X)

Lo mthi uvela eMzantsi Afrika emantla kunye naseBotswana esemazantsi. Uqhele ukufumaneka kwiAlbany thicket, Indian Ocean coastal belt kunye ne-savanna biomes.

Unegalelo eliphakathi kwi-biodiversity, njengoko iintyatyambo zawo zitsala izinambuzane, kwaye iziqhamo ezithambileyo zidliwa ziintaka.

Iintyatyambo zithuthwa ikakhulu zii-honeybees, kwaye imbewu yawo ihanjiswa ziintaka ezitya iziqhamo.

Lo mthi uyahlala amagqabi (deciduous), nto leyo ethetha ukuba ungatyalwa apho ufuna khona ilanga ebusika kunye nomthunzi ehlotyeni.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Lo mthi unokunyamezela uluhlu olubanzi lwemozulu phakathi kwe-10°C ukuya kwi-35°C.

Ufuna imvula ephakathi kwe-800mm ne-1,200mm ngonyaka, kodwa unokumelana nebalela ethile.

Uthanda ukukhanya kwelanga elipheleleyo, kodwa unokunyamezela ithunzi elincinane.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Ukhula kakuhle kumhlaba omhle ophuma amanzi kakuhle, owesanti kunye ne-loam.

Iimeko ezifanelekileyo ze-pH kulo mthi ziphakathi kwe-5 ne-7 (eyi-asidi).

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Ingakhuliswa kwimbewu ecoceke kakuhle, eyomisiwe ethunzini, emva koko icandwe kancinci (scarified) kwaye icwiliswe emanzini ubusuku bonke phambi kokutyala.

Imbewu ihluma malunga neentsuku ezi-14.

Amasebe anzima kunye nawaphakathi anokusikwa entlakohlaza nasehlotyeni, aze anyangwe ngehloni yokukhula.

Isityalo sikhula malunga ne-550mm ngonyaka kwaye sifikelela ekugqibeleni kwaso emva kweminyaka emi-5 okanye nangaphezulu.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela: <https://pza.sanbi.org/cordia-caffra>

Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, PlantZAfrica, Wikimedia Commons

UMNINI

Berchemia zeyheri (L), red ivorywood (E), umnini (X)

Umnini ubukhulu becala ufumaneka kumantla eMzantsi Afrika, eZimbabwe naseMozambique, kwiindawo ezinehlathi, iBushveld, kwiindawo ezinamawa, nakwiingxangxasi zamanzi kunye nemilambo.

Iziqhamo zaso zimalunga ne-1cm ubukhulu, ziveliswa ngamakhama okanye amaqela ukusuka ngolanuwari ukuya kuAprili kwaye zidlwa zingaphekwangqa.

Lo mthi ukhula ukuya kubude obuyi-8m kwaye unamagatya okanye amahlala asesiphakathi okanye axineneyo.

Ngenxa yenkqubo yawo yeengcambu ezisabalalayo okungephi, iindebe ezikhuselayo neziqhamo, ilungele ukutyalwa ezikolweni nasezindaweni zikawonke-wonke.

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUQHAMBA				
Dec	Jan	Feb	☀️	
Mar	Apr	May	🌿	
Jun	Jul	Aug	❄️	
Sep	Oct	Nov	🌸	

IMPILO NOKUTYA

Iziqhamo zaso zizele yi-vitamin C, eninzi kangangaleyo efunyanwa kwi-apile, kunye ne-vitamin B, enceda impilo kwimithambo kunye nentliziyo.

Iquletse i-calcium, i-magnesium, i-iron, i-phosphorus, i-potassium kunye ne-zinc, ukomeleza igazi, amathambo kunye nezihlunu.

Iyimithombo elungileyo ye-fiber kunye neprotheyini ukunyusa amandla omzimba.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Lo mthi lungele ukuvelisa umthunzi obalulekileyo ezindaweni zokulima nasezindaweni zokuhlala.

Iinkuni zawo zisetyenziswa ekwenzeni iintsika zocingo kunye nezixhobo ezahlukeneyo.

Unokusebenza njengesithintelo esisebenzayo sokuthintela umoya onamandla.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Amagqabi, iintyatyambo, iziqhamo kunye nexolo zidliwa zizinambuzane, iintaka nezilwanyana.

Uhlala eluhlaza unyaka wonke okanye uphantse uwise amagqabi ngamanye amaxesha, kwaye uyaxhathisa kwimozulu eyomileyo.

Ungatyalwa ukunceda ekuthinteleni ukhukuliseko lomhlaba.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/berchemia-zeyheri>
 Imifanekiso: Wikimedia Commons,
 iSpotnature

UMNINI

Berchemia zeyheri (L), red ivorywood (E), umnini (X)

Lo mthi uvela eMzantsi Afrika, eMozambique naseZimbabwe kwaye uqhele ukufumaneka kwimimandla yehlathi elimalunga noLwandle lwaselIndian ocean nakwii-savanna biomes, ngakumbi kwiinduli ezijonge emazantsi nasempuma.

Iintyatyambo ziyimithombo yokutya yezinambuzane, ngelixa iziqhamo ezivuthiweyo zithandwa ziintaka, iimfene kunye neebushbabies. Amagqabi adliwa ziindlulamthi, ama-Eland, amaKudu, iNyala, amaBushbuck kunye neempala. I Porcupines zitya amaxolo.

Imbewu isasazwa ziintaka ezitya iziqhamo.

Imbewu yokutyalala ingasuswa ngokususa intlama (pulp) kwizinqhamo ezivuthiweyo.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Uluhlu lobushushu olufanelekileyo kukuba phakathi kwe-22°C ne-28°C, kodwa ungamelana neemeko ezisusela kwi-15°C ukuya kwi-34°C.

Ukhula bhetele phantsi kweemeko zemvula eziphakathi okanye eziphezulu, eziphakathi kwe-0-35mm ngeveki.

Uthanda ukutyalwa phantsi kwelanga elipheleleyo.

Uthi uvakalelwe ebusika kwaye uya kufuna ukhuseleko kwiindawo ezibandayo.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Uthanda umhlaba onetyuwa encinci (loamy) okanye isanti ephuma amanzi kakhule.

Iimeko ezifanelekileyo zifuna i-pH ephakathi kwe-4 ne-7.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Imbewu kufuneka ihlanzwe kuqala phambi kokutyalala.

Imbewu entsha idla ngokuhluma phakathi kweentsuku ezi-5 nezi-9.

Izithole kunye nezityalo ezincinci azidingi manzi amaninzi.

Ukhula ngesantya esiphakathi phantsi kweemeko ezilungileyo zokuncenkceshela.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/berchemia-zeyheri>
 Imifanekiso: Wikimedia Commons,
 iSpotnature

UMNJOMI

Syzygium cordatum (L), water berry, water pear (E), injomi, umdoni (X)

Umthi lo ufumaneka kumbindi nasemazantsi eAfrika kufuphi namanzi acocekileyo, ecaleni kwemilambo, emithaneni yemithi, nakwiinduli ezinamahlathi.

Izityalo ziqala ukuvela ukusuka ngoDisemba ukuya kuApreli kwaye zingatywa ziluhlaza.

Lo mthi mkhulu unokukhula ukuya kubude obuziimitha ezili-15 kwaye une-canopy enkulu kakhulu.

Ubude bawo, ulwandiso lwe-canopy, inkqubo yeengcambu enobundlongondlongo kunye nokukhula kwesiqhamo esikhulu kuyenza ingafaneleki kufuphi nezakhiwo, iindlela nezixhobo zengingqi.

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUQHAMBA

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Esi siqhamo sinika amandla omzimba ngenxa yokuba sinevithamini A, B, C no-E eziphezulu eziphucula imisebenzi yeeseli (cells) zomzimba.

Sisiseko esilungileyo sentsimbi (iron), i-magnesium, kunye ne-potassium ezomeleza amathambo, igazi kunye nezihlunu.

Ixolo lawo linezakhiwo zokuphilisa izifo ezinjengo-tyatyazo, iingxaki zamathumbu, intloko ebuhlungu, ukungafumani ixesha lokuya exesheni, amanxeba kunye neengxaki zokuphefumla.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Umthi usetyenziswa ukwenza izibonda zokubiya kunye nezixhobo.

I-canopy enkulu ethe sapha inika umthunzi oluncedo.

Isiqhamo nexolo kusetyenziswa ukovelisa idayi eluhlaza okwesibhakabhaka.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Umthi uyanyamezela kumanzi amileyo (waterlogged) kwaye usetyenziswa ukunciphisa ukhukuliseko lomhlaba kufuphi nemilambo.

Umthi uyamelana nomlilo kwaye ungasetyenziswa njengomqobo womoya.

Kukholelwa ukuba lo mthi ubonisa ubukho bamanzi angaphantsi komhlaba.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/syzygium-cordatum>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

UMNJOMI

Syzygium cordatum (L), water berry, water pear (E), injomi, umdoni (X)

Umnjomi usuka eAfrika esembindini nasezantsi kwaye ukhula kwiindawo ezikufuphi nonxweme lweLwandlekazi lwase i- Indian ocean kunye nemimandla ye-savanna.

Iindidi ezininzi zeentaka zitya esi siqhamo, izinambuzane zitsalwa ziintyatyambo, kwaye izilwanyana zitya amasebe kunye neziqhamo.

Iintyatyambo zithwalwa ziintaka nezinye izinambuzane, kwaye imbewu isasazwa ziintaka nezilwanyana ezityayo.

Ngenxa yokuba lo mthi utsala iindidi ezininzi zeentaka, izinambuzane nezilwanyana, qiniseka ukuba uyawutyala kude nekhaya.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Umthi uyakwazi ukumelana nemozulu ephakathi, eneqondo lobushushu eliphakathi kwe-10°C ukuya kwi-35°C.

Ukhula kakuhle kwindawo enemvula ephakathi kwe-600mm ukuya kwi-1,500mm kwaye uyakwazi ukumelana namanzi amaninzi.

Uthanda ukukhanya kwelanga ngokupheleleyo okanye ukukhanya kwangentsasa kwaye uyamelana nesithunzi esincinci.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Umthi ukhula kakuhle kumhlaba wesanti okanye umhlaba one-loam.

Uthanda umhlaba one-pH ephakathi kwe-5 kunye ne-7.5.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA

Ukusasazwa kweziqhamo kulungile xa kusetyenziswa imbewu entsha ephilayo eyomisiweyo.

Imbewu entsha ithatha malunga neentsuku ezingama-25 ukuze iqhakaze.

Izityalo ezincinci kunye neembewu zifuna ukunkencneshelwa rhoqo.

Isantya sokukhula siyakhawuleza kwaye umthi unokukhula nge-1m ngonyaka phantsi kweemeko ezifanelekileyo zokukhula.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/syzygium-cordatum>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

UMPAYI / AMAKHIWANE

Ficus natalensis (L), Natal fig, forest fig (E), umpayi, amakhiwane (X)

Lo mthi ufumaneka kulo lonke elaseMpuma Afrika, kumahlathi amanzi nomileyo, kwii thicket, kumahlathi akufuphi nemilambo, nakwiindawo ezinemvula eninzi kwi-savanna, ukuya kubude obuyi-2,200m.

Iziqhamo ezinobukhulu obuyi-1cm, ziveliswa ngamaqela ukususela ngoJulayi ukuya kuDisemba, kwaye zinokutyiwa ziluhlaza, zenziwe ijusi okanye ijam.

Ukhula ube ngumthi omkhulu ofikelela kwi-20m, kunye necanopy enkulu esasazekayo.

Ngenxa yenkqubo yeengcambu ezindlongondlongo, ukuphakama kunye nendlela yokukhula, lo mthi akufuneki utyalwe kufutshane neziseko zophuhliso.

IXESHA LOKUQHAMBA				
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IMPILO NOKUTYA

- Iziqhamo ziqulethe ikhalsiyam, iron, imagniziyam, ifosforasi kunye nepotasiyam, ezibalulekileyo ekomelezeni amathambo nezihlunu.
- Amagqabi asetyenziswa ukunyanga iingxaki zokugaya ukutya kwaye ayasetyenziselwa ukunyanga amanxeba.
- Umxube weempande zomthi usetyenziswa ukunyanga amehlo.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

- Umthi une-canopy enkulu kakhulu, efanelekileyo ekwenzeni ithunzi.
- Ulusu/ixolo lwawo lisetyenziswa ekwenzeni ilaphu lezikhuni (barkcloth), into esetyenziswa kushishino lwefashoni.
- Ixolo/uluso luphinda lusetyenziswe njengamayeza onyango okukhohlela okunamandla, umkhuhlane, kunye nokukhuthaza imveliso yobisi kwiinkomo.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

- Izinambuzane kunye neentaka ezininzi zityela i-nectar yawo, kwaye iziqhamo zitya ziintaka kunye namalulwane.
- Amawasp athwala iintyatyambo zawo, anokuzalela ngaphakathi kweziqhamo ukuze aphindaphinde.
- Lo mthi awuhlali uphalaza amagqabi, uyakwazi ukumelana nemimoya emikhulu kwaye ungasetyenziswa njengesithinteli somoya (windbreak).

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/ficus-natalensis>
 Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

UMPAYI / AMAKHIWANE

Ficus natalensis (L), Natal fig, forest fig (E), umpayi, amakhiwane (X)

Lo mthi uvela eAfrika kwaye ufumaneka kwi-savanna nasehlathini.

Unegalelo elikhulu kwindalo njengomthombo wokutya kwezinambuzane, ngakumbi amawasp, iintaka, kunye namalulwane.

Ukwanda kwawo kwenziwa ngama-wasp, athatha amaqanda awo awafake ngaphakathi kweziquhamo. Umthi ukhula phakathi kwamasebe emithi emide, emva koko uwisa iingcambu zawo phantsi emhlabeni.

Ungatyalwa ngokusikwa okanye imbewu eqokelelwe phakathi kukaSeptemba noNovemba.

Ngenxa yokuba utsala amawasp, qiniseka ukuba awutyalwa kufutshane nezindlu.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

- Umthi ukhula kakuhle kwiindawo ezitshisayo nezinezozulu epholileyo.
- Lo mthi uyakwazi ukulungelelanisa kwaye ungakhula kwiindawo ezinemvula ephantsi okanye epehuzulu.
- Uthanda ukukhula elangeni ngokupheleleyo kodwa ungamelana nethunzi elincinci.
- Akudingeki ukuba unakekelwe kakhulu kuba umelana nexesha lesomiso.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

- Umthi ukhula kakuhle kwimihlaba enokukhupha amanzi kakuhle nasezindaweni ezinamanzi asezantsi komhlaba amaninzi.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

- Imbewu eqokelelwe kwiqhamo ezivuthiweyo ihluma phakathi kweentsuku eziyi-15 ukuya kwi-90.
- Ingakhuliswa nangokusikwa okuthathwe kumasebe aze aphathwe ngehomboni, kwaye ukhule lula malunga neenyanga eziyi-12 ukuya kweziyi-18.
- Ifuna amanzi rhoqo kwiminyaka emine yokuqala kwiindawo ezinemvula eziphakathi.
- Ukhula ngokukhawuleza, malunga ne-0.5m ukuya kwi-1m ngonyaka, kwaye ufikelela ebudaleni emva kweminyaka emine.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/ficus-natalensis>
 Imfanekiso: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

UMPHAFA

Ziziphus mucronata (L), buffalo thorn (E), umphafa (X)

Lo mthi ufumaneka kulo lonke elaseMzantsi Afrika kwiindawo ezahlukeneyo ezifana namahlathi, amazantsi avulekileyo, iinduli ezinemiqolomba, kunye namadlelo, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-2,000m ngaphezu komphakamo wolwandle.

Nangona lo mthi uvelisa iziqhamo, azinambitheki kakhulu. Lo mthi mkhulu unokukhula ufinyelele kwi-10m ubude, kwaye unemithunzi enobubanzi. Amasebe awo anameva.

Inkqubo yengcambu yawo ayinamandla kakhulu, nto leyo eyenza ulungele ukutyalwa kufutshane nezikolo nemibhobho yamanzi, kodwa hayi phantsi kwemigca yamandla okanye ecaleni kweendlela ngenxa yobude bawo kunye nokusasazeka kwawo kwamasebe anameva.

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IMPILO NOKUTYA

- Ingumthombo otyebileyo wekalsiyam, i-ayini, imagniziyam kunye nepotassium, ezibalulekileyo ekomelezeni amathambo nasempilweni yegazi.
- Iingcambu ngamanye amaxa zisetyenziswa njengeyeza lokunciphisa iintlungu.
- Ixolo kunye namagqabi zisetyenziswa ekuphiliseni izilonda kwaye zifakwa njengebandishi.
- Imbewu ngamanye amaxesha iyosiwa (roasted) isetyenziswe kwindawo yekofu.
- Umgubo omnandi ojikeleze imbewu unokwenziwa iphalishi enempi.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

- Amagqabi asetyenziswa njengokutya kwezilwanyana zasekhaya.
- Amasebe asetyenziswa kwizithethe zokungcwaba nakwiinkqubo zonxibelelwano nemimoya yezinyanya.
- Umthi usetyenziselwa iinkuni zomlilo, kunye nokwenziwa kwezibonda zocingo nezixhobo.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

- Lo mthi ungumthombo obalulekileyo we-nectar yezinambuzane, ulungele ukufuywa kweenyosi.
- Ngenxa yobumxinwa nameva, unokutyalwa njengocingo oluphilayo olungangenekiyo ukuze kuthintelwe izilwanyana ekungneneni.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/ziziphus-mucronata>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes

UMPHAFA

Ziziphus mucronata (L), buffalo thorn (E), umphafa (X)

Lo mthi uvela e-Afrika kwaye ufumaneka kwi-Albany thicket, fynbos, amathafa, ummandla wonxweme loLwandlekazi l -indian ocean, iKaroo, isavanna kunye neSucculent Karoo biomes.

Udlala indima ebalulekileyo kwindalo ngokuba likhaya lezilwanyana zasendle kunye nomthombo wokutya kweentaka, imihlambi yezilwanyana kunye neenkomo ezitya amagqabi kunye neziqhamo zawo.

Iintyatyambo zawo zipollinated ziinyosi, kwaye imbewu isasazwa ziintaka kunye nezilwanyana ezitya iziqhamo.

Ngenxa yokuba itsala izinambuzane, iintaka nezilwanyana ezahlukahlukeneyo, kungcono ukutyalwa kulo mthi kude nendlu ukuze uhlale unobuhlobo nezilwanyana zasendle.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Lo mthi uthanda imozulu epholileyo ukuya kweyaphakathi, enobushushu obuphakathi kwe-12°C ukuya kwi-30°C.

Ukhetha imvula yonyaka ephakathi kwe-440mm kunye ne-1,200mm.

Umthi ukhula kakuhle xa utyalwe elangeni elipheleleyo.

Lo mthi uyakwazi ukuzivumelanisa neemeko ezahlukeneyo kwaye unokumelana nokubanda okumandla kunye nexeshana elide lembalela.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Lo mthi uthanda umhlaba onesanti kunye nowothuli, kodwa unokunyamezela naluphi na olunye uhlobo lomhlaba oluhamba kakuhle amanzi.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Njengoko imbewu ingagcinwa ixesha elide, kungcono ukusebenzisa imbewu entsha.

Imbewu kufuneka iqhekeke kwinqokoma (nut) yayo kwaye ifakwe emanzini ashushu ubusuku bonke phambi kokutyala.

Imbewu idla ngokuhluma phakathi kweeveki ezimbini.

Izityalo ezisakhulayo zifuna ukunkcenkceshelwa ngendlela ephakathi.

Lo mthi ukhula kancinci kwaye unokufikelela kwi-30cm ngonyaka.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/ziziphus-mucronata>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes

UMQOKOLO

Dovyalis caffra (L), Kei apple (E), umqokolo (X)

Umqokolo ufumaneka kwimimandla esemazantsi nasempuma eMzantsi Afrika, ukhula kwiindawo ezomileyo, kwiindawo ezinengca enehlathi, nakwiimphetho zamahlathi, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-2,450m.

Iziqhamo zikhula ngobuninzi zizinze ngamaqela, ngalinye limalunga ne-6cm ububanzi, ukususela ngoNovemba ukuya kuJanuwari, kwaye zingatywiwa ziluhlaza, zenziwe iijusi, okanye zigcinwe.

Lo mthi-uhlhlana ukhula malunga ne-4m ukuphakama, kwaye usasaza amasebe awo axineneyo kunye nameva ngokuphinda- phinda.

Ngenxa yokuphakama kwawo okuphakathi kunye nokulahla amagqabi ngokungangcolisiyo, ungatyalwa kufutshane neentambo zombane namanzi, izakhiwo kunye neendlela.

IXESHA LOKUQHAMBA			
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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Uqulethe iivithamini A noB ezibalulekileyo emehlweni, kulusu, kwiingcambu zeenwele, kwiihomoni nasekusebenzeni kwengqondo.

Utyebile kwiVitamin C (amaxesha asixhenxe kune orinji) enceda ekomelezeni inkqubo yokuzikhusela komzimba.

Uqulethe i-calcium kunye ne-phosphorus ezinqinisa amathambo negazi.

Uneprotein kunye nefayibha ezixhasa impilo yemisispha nesistim yemizwa.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Amagqabi namasebe zisetyenziswa njengesidlo seenkomo ngexesha lesomiso.

Iintyatyambo zitsala iinyosi ezibalulekileyo ekusasazeni imbewu, zilungele ekufuyweni kweenyosi.

Uyamelana nexesha elomileyo nelinqhwa.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Wenza uthango olugqwesileyo okanye uthango oluphilayo olugcina izilwanyana kunye nezilwanyana zasekhaya zingangeni.

Iintaka zitya iziqhamo, kunye nezinambuzane ezitsalwa ngumthi.

Izilwanyana ezifana nee antelope kunye neenkawu zitya iziqhamo kwaye zisasaza imbewu.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<http://pza.sanbi.org/dovyalis-caffra>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, PlantZAfrica

UMQOKOLO

Dovyalis caffra (L), Kei apple (E), umqokolo (X)

Umqokolo uvela eMzantsi Afrika kwaye uyafumaneka kwiindawo ze-Albany thicket, grassland, Indian Ocean coastal belt, savanna, kunye ne-Succulent Karoo.

Lo mthi ungumthombo wokutya kwezinzambuzane (intyatyambo), ngelixa iintaka kunye nezilwanyana ezinkulu zisitya iziqhamo.

Esisityalo sinentyantyambo ezingomama nezingotata kwaye uthuli lwetyatyambo luthwalwa zizinambuzane.

Kungcono sityalwe ngamaqela ukuze kwandiswe imveliso yeziqhamo.

Njengokuba sithandwa ziintaka, izinzambuzane nezilwanyana, kungcono ukusityala kude nekhaya ukuze kungabikho ngxaki phakathi kwabantu nezilwanyana zasendle.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Esi sityalo siyakwazi ukumelana neemeko zemozulu ezahlukeneyo kwaye sithanda ubushushu obuphakathi kwe-10°C ukuya kwi-35°C.

Siphumelela kwiindawo ezinemvula ephakathi kwe-700mm ukuya kwi-1,300mm ngonyaka.

Lo mthi-uhlahlana (shrub) uthanda ilanga elipheleleyo, ukunyamezela ukoma, kwaye ukwazi nokukhula kwindawo enesithunzi esincinci.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Umqokolo uthanda ukutyalwa kwindawo enomhlaba onentlabathi okanye onetyuwa othambileyo kodwa one-drainage efanelekileyo.

Uthanda i-pH ephakathi kwe-5 ne-7 ukuze ukhule ngokugqwesileyo.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Esi sityalo sinokuhlwayelwa kwimbewu ecocekileyo neyomiswe kwindawo enethunzi.

Imbewu iya kuhluma phakathi kweentsuku eziyi-18 ne-20.

Ingakhuliswa nangokuthatha amahlumelo aqinileyo afakwe kwihomoni yokukhula.

Isityalo sikhula nge-60cm ngonyaka kwaye sifikelela ekuvuthweni emva kweminyaka eyi-4.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:

<http://pza.sanbi.org/dovyalis-caffra>

Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, PlantZAfrica

UMQOKOLO WASEAFRIKA

Garcinia livingstonei (L), African mangosteen (E), amabimbi (X)

Umthi lo ufumaneka kwiindawo ezininzi zommandla oshushu waseAfrika, kwaye ukhula kwiindawo ezinezihlahla ezomileyo, kwihlathi elivulekileyo nasehlathini, ukuya kuthi ga kubude obuyi-1,900m.

Isiqhamo silinganiselwa kwi-2.5cm ngobukhulu, sivela ngamaqela ukusuka ngoNovemba ukuya kuJanuwari, kwaye siyadiwa singaphekhwanga, sisenziwa ijusi okanye ijam.

Lo mthi ukhula ukusuka kubukhulu obuphakathi ukuya kwi-7m okanye nangaphezulu, unamagqabi amaninzi kwaye unokuvuleka.

Ngokuvuleka okuphakathi kunye nenkqubo yeempande ezingekho ndlongondlongo, lo mthi ulungele ukutyalwa kufutshane neendlela, izakhiwo kunye nezibonelelo zoncendo lwasezidolophini.

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUQHAMBA

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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Iziqhamo ziqulathe iivithamini A, B, kunye noC, ezibalulekileyo kulusu olusempilweni, amathambo, igazi kunye nokomeleza amajoni omzimba.

Iziqhamo zikwane-calcium, magnesium kunye ne-zinc, ezibalulekileyo kumathambo nemisipha.

Ingcambu yayo egutyiweyo yomiswa isetyenziswa njengesiyobisi sokuvusa inkanuko.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Lo mthi awupheli magqabi unokukhula ube ngumthi omkhulu owenza umthunzi okanye utyalwe njengomqobo womoya.

Umthi usetyenziswa ekwenzeni izigxina zocingo kunye nezixhobo.

Isiqhamo singavundiswa sibe sisiselo esinxilisayo.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Umthi utsala iinyosi, iibhabhathane, iintaka nezilwanyana, nto leyo exhasa iintlobo ngeentlobo zezidalwa zendalo.

Amagqabi axineneyo enza ufaneleke ukutyalwa njenge-heji.

Lo mthi uyakwazi ukumelana nembalela, oko kuthetha ukuba unokunceda ekuzinziseni umhlaba nasekubuyiseleni iindawo ezonakeleyo.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/garcinia-livingstonei>
 Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, PlantZAfrica,
 Wikimedia Commons

UMQOKOLO WASEAFRIKA

Garcinia livingstonei (L), African mangosteen (E), amabimbi (X)

Lo mthi ufumaneka kulo lonke elingasezantsi kweAfrika, kwi-Albany thicket, emadlelweni, i-savanna kunye nehlathi elivulekileyo.

Iintyatyambo ezityebileyo kwinektara zitsala izinambuzane ezininzi ezisisasazayo. Iziqhamo ezivuthiweyo zidliwa ziintaka nezilwanyana, ezisisaza imbewu.

Umthi lo uyi- dioecious—ukuthetha ukuba umthi ngamnye uvelisa iintyatyambo zesini esinye kuphela (ezimadoda okanye ezingomama) kwaye uxhomekeke kwizinambuzane ukuze uzivelise.

Kungoko kubalulekile ukutyala imithi emininzi kufutshane ukuze kwande isiqhamo.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

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Sep	Oct	Nov	

IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Lo mthi uthanda umoya oshushu, oneqondo lobushushu eliphakathi kwe-15°C kunye ne-25°C.

Uthanda imvula ephakathi kwe-800mm kunye ne-1,800mm ngonyaka.

Uthanda ukukhanya kwelanga ngokupheleleyo, kodwa unyamezela isiqingatha somthunzi kwaye awuthandi imozulu ebandayo.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Umthi ungakhula kwiindidi ezahlukeneyo zomhlaba, ukuba nje zikhupha amanzi kakuhle.

Uthanda umhlaba one-pH ephakathi kwe-5 kunye ne-6, ethande ukuba ne-asidi kancinci okanye ibe-neutral.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Imbewu entsha ihluma kwiinyanga ezintandathu.

Ukusikwa kwesebe kufakwe iihomoni zokukhula kwaye iinduku zayo zikhula lula.

Ukugraftha kuvumela ukuba kuhlale kuhluma iintyatyambo zesini esibini emthini omnye, nto leyo ekhuthaza ukuzala kweziqhamo.

Izithole nemithi eselula kufuneka ifumane amanzi ngokwaneleyo.

Ukhula kancinci, kwaye uthatha malunga neminyaka emi-2 ukuba ube mdala xa ugrafthiwe okanye usikwa, kwaye iminyaka emi-4 xa ukhule embewini.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/garcinia-livingstonei>
 Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, PlantZAfrica,
 Wikimedia Commons

UMSIMBITHI

Milletia grandis (L), umzimbeet (E), umsimbithi (X)

Lo mthi ufumaneka KwaZulu-Natal naseMpuma Koloni, kwaye uxhaphake Mpondoland, kwiindawo ezifika kwi-600m ngaphezu komphakamo wolwandle.

Iziqhamo zivelisa iingqayi ezimalunga ne-15cm ubude, eziqulethe imbewu engatyiwayo kwaye enetyhefu.

Lo mthi ukhula ngokukhawuleza kwaye unokufikelela kwi-10m ubude, unegqabi elisasazekayo elikhulu.

Ngenxa yobude bawo kunye ne-canopy enkulu, akufanelekanga ukuba utyalwe kufutshane neengcingo zombane. Inkqubo yengcambu engeyiyo enobundlongondlongo kunye nomthamo ophantsi wokulahlala amagqabi yenza ukuba ifaneleke ukutyalwa kufuphi nezikolo kunye nemibhobho yamanzi.

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUQHAMBA				
Dec	Jan	Feb	☀️	
Mar	Apr	May	🌿	
Jun	Jul	Aug	❄️	
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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Imbewu yalo mthi ayityiwa kuba inetyhefu.

Ingcambu egayiweyo ingasetyenziswa njengeyeza lokubulala iintlanzi ngotolo olunetyhefu, kodwa iintlanzi kufuneka ziphekwe ngaphambi kokutyiwa.

Imbewu egayiweyo (isetyenziswa ngononophelo) iyanyuswa nobisi kwaye isetyenziswa kunyango lweentsholongwane zamathumbu.

Umxube wengcambu ungasetyenziswa ukukhuthaza ukulala.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Umthi wawo usetyenziswa ekwenzeni ifanitshala, izibonda zocingo, iiplanga, kunye nezixhobo ezincinci.

Umthi ofanelekileyo wokubonelela ngomthunzi okanye indawo yokhuseleko.

Umthi wawo omhle usetyenziswa ekwenzeni izixhobo zokuhamba ezithengiselwa abatyeleli.

Iingcambu zinceda ekubuyiseleni i-nitrogen emhlabeni.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Iingqayi zembewu zenza indawo efanelekileyo yokuzalela iimpukane kwanamabhathathane.

Imithi ingatyalwa ngokulandelelana ukwenza uthango oluphilayo okanye umqobo womoya.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/milletia-grandis>

Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes,
Wikimedia Commons

UMSIMBITHI

Milletia grandis (L), umzimbeet (E), umsimbithi (X)

Umsimbithi uvela KwaZulu-Natal naseMpuma Koloni kwaye ufumaneka kwi-biome yonxweme loLwandlekazi l- Indian ocean.

Unceda kakhulu kwindalo njengoko unikezela ukutya kwimibungu yamabhabhathane ezityayo amagqabi, nakwinkawu.

Iintyatyambo zawo ezityebileyo nge-nectar zisasazwa lula zizinambuzane.

Iimbewu ziveliswa kwiingqayi ukusukela ngoFebruwari ukuya kuJulayi, kwaye zisasazwa ngokwendalo ngumoya namanzi.

Lo mthi oyinxalenye yesemi-deciduous kwaye unaba kakhulu, kufuneka utsyalwe kwiindawo ezivulekileyo.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Lo mthi ukhula kakuhle kwimozulu eshushu nephakathi nendawo, kwe-10°C - 35°C.

Uthanda iindawo ezinemvula eninzi unyaka wonke.

Uthanda ukukhanya kwelanga ngokupheleleyo kodwa uyakwazi ukunyamezela isithunzi esincinci.

Umthi onzima onokumelana nomkhenkce omncinci.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Ukhula kakuhle kumhlaba onesanti kunye nomhlaba we-loam.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Umthi lo uphehlwa lula ngembewu entsha.

Iimbewu entsha kufuneka ifakwe emanzi ashushu ubusuku bonke ngaphambi kokutyala, kwaye ihluma lula.

Izityalo ezincinci mazifumane amanzi rhoqo.

Lo mthi ukhula ngokukhawuleza, unokufikelela phakathi kwi-80cm - 1m ngonyaka phantsi kweemeko ezifanelekileyo.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela: <https://pza.sanbi.org/millettia-grandis>
Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, Wikimedia Commons

UMSINTSI

Erythrina lysistemon (L), coral tree (E), umsinsi (X)

Lo mthi ufumaneka kulo lonke amazantsi leAfrika, kwiinduli ezinesanti eziselunxwemeni, kwiindawo eziluhlaza ezinomhlaba onehlathi, indawo ezineehlathi ezilahla amagqabi ebusika, nasehlathini elivulekileyo, ukuya kubude obuyi-1,950m.

Isiqhamo asidliwa, kwaye sivela njengeengxowa zeembewu ezibhityileyo ezimalunga ne-150-200mm ubude, ziveliswa kwiindidi.

Igama lalo mthi lisusela kwiintyatyambo zawo ezibomvu ezimangalisayo ezivelayo entwasahlobo. Uyakwazi ukufikelela kwi-7m okanye nangaphezulu phantsi kweemeko ezifanelekileyo.

Inkqubo yeengcambu ephakathi, lo mthi ungalinywa kufutshane nezakhiwo, iindlela, kunye nezibonelelo zophuhliso lwengingqi.

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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Isiselo esenziwe ngamahlamvu okanye ngamagqabi kunye nexolo sikholeleka ekuncedeni ukukhuthaza xa kuncediswa ukuzalwa komntwana.

Amagqabi awo aqulethe izithako ezichasene nokudumba kunye neentsholongwane.

Umdibaniso wamahlamvu okanye amagqabi alo mthi usetyenziswa ekunyangelweni kweentlungu zendlebe.

Iingcambu zawo zisetyenziswa ekunyangelweni kweengxaki zamathambo, kwaye ixolo lisetyenziswa ukunyanga amanxeba nezilonda.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Lo mthi uthathwa njengesimboli yobukhosi kwaye utyalwa emangcwabeni eenkosi zakwaZulu.

Iimbewu zawo, ezaziwa njenge "zethamsanqa," zisetyenziswa njengentsimbi zokuhombisa.

Ukudubula kwawo kusebenza njengasalathiso esihle sokuba lixesha lokutyala izityalo.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Iintaka ezifana nee-barbets kunye nee-woodpeckers zizalela kwimiqolo yemthi efileyo, kwaye amaqela eenyosi ahlala kwiimbobo zemiqolo yomthi.

Ngamasebe anameva, akhula ngokungakhawulezi, lo mthi ungalinywa njengothango oluphilayo.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/erythrina-lysisstemon>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes

UMSINTSI

Erythrina lysistemon (L), coral tree (E), umsinsi (X)

Lo mthi uphuma emazantsi eAfrika kwaye ufumaneka kwimimandla yommandla ongaselwandle i-Indian ocean.

Uvelisa i-nectar enceda izinambuzane kunye neentaka, ngelixa iinkawu zasevervet zitya iintyatyambo zawo eziselula. Ezinye izilwanyana ezihlala ehlathini, njengeenyamakazi, zidla amagqabi awo, ngelixa ooRhino, ooNdlovu, kunye nooBaboon bedla ixolo, kwaye iihagu zasehlathini zidla iingcambu.

Iintyatyambo zalo mthi zisasazwa zizinambuzane neentaka, kwaye iparrot enentloko emdaka idla kwaye isasaza imbewu yalo.

Ungatyalwa kwiindawo apho ufumana ilanga ebusika kwaye nomthunzi ehlotyeni.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Lo mthi unokunyamezela amaqondo obushushu aphakathi kwe-10°C ne-35°C.

Ukukhula kakuhle kufuna imvula ephuzulu ngexesha lasehlotyeni.

Ungakhula kwindawo enelanga elipheleleyo okanye kwisiqingatha somthunzi.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Ungakhula kwiindidi ezahlukeneyo zomhlaba okhupha amanzi kakuhle.

Iingcambu zawo zineda ukufaka i-nitrogen emhlabeni, nto leyo eluncedo ekuphuculeni umhlaba.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Imbewu kufuneka icwiliswe emanzini ubusuku bonke phambi kokuba ihlwanyelwe, kwaye ithatha ixesha elide ukuhluma.

Ingakhuliswa lula ngokusikwa ifakwe iihomoni ngasekupheleni kwentwasahlobo ukuya ehlotyeni, okanye ngokugxunyekwa ekwindla ukuya entwasahlobo.

Izityalo eziselula zifuna amanzi aphakathi ukuze zikhule kakuhle.

Phantsi kweemeko ezifanelekileyo, lo mthi ukhula ngokukhawuleza, phakathi kwe-1 ukuya kwi-1.5m ngonyaka.

Imithi eselula isengozini yeqabaka kwaye ifuna ukukhuselwa kwiindawo ezibandayo.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/erythrina-lysisitemon>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes

UMTENATANE

Diospyros whyteana (L), bladder nut (E), umtenatane (X)

Lo mthi uxhaphake kumazantsi eAfrika kwaye ufumaneka kwiindawo ezihlala ziluhlaza unyaka wonke, kwihlathi leentaba, nakwiindawo ezinamahlathi aphantsi ukuya kubude obuyi-2,400m.

Izqhamo zivela phakathi kukaJanuwari no-Aprili, zimalunga ne-2cm ubukhulu kwaye ziqulathe iqokobhe eligqatywe njengeblada, elidliwayo lingekho phantsi kwenkqubo yokuphekwa.

Lo mthi ukhula ngokukhawuleza, awupheli magqabi kwaye ungakhula ufikelela kubude obuyi-3m.

Indlela yawo yokukhula kunye nenkqubo yeempande ezincinci ivumela ukuba utyalwe kufutshane nezakhiwo, izikolo, iindlela, imigca yonikezelo lombane kunye nemibhobho yamanzi.

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Umthi lo uqulethe ifayibha, iprotheyini kunye ne-amino acids eziluncedo kwinkqubo yokugaya ukutya.

Igxolo lawo lisetyenziswa kunyango lwemveli ukunceda intlungu yexesha, ukungazali nokungakhulelisi.

Amagqabi kunye neengcambu zaso zisetyenziswa kunyango lwesikhumba.

Iimbewu ezitshisiweyo zisetyenziswa kwindawo yekofu.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Isiqhamo esimuncu kwaye asidliwa kakhulu kodwa sisetyenziswa ekwenzeni imibala yokudaya.

Umthi usetyenziswa ekwenzeni izigxina zocingo, izixhobo, kunye nezinto zokuhombisa ikhaya.

Ukhula kakuhle xa usikwa rhoqo, nto leyo eyenza ulungele ukwenziwa isithinteli.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Iintyatyambo zawo zitsala izinambuzane ezinceda ekuzalaneni, ezifana neenyosi kunye neebhabhathane, nto leyo ekwatsala neentaka.

Ukhula njengesihlahla esinzima, nto leyo enika iintaka indawo yokuhlala kunye nokuzalela.

Lo mthi unokunika ukhuseleko kwiindawo ezivulekileyo njengendawo yokuphumla nanjengomqobo womoya.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/diospyros-whyteana>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes

UMTENATANE

Diospyros whyteana (L), bladder nut (E), umtenatane (X)

Umtenatane uvela emazantsi eAfrika kwaye ufumaneka kwi-Albany thicket, i-fynbos, emadlelweni, ummandla ongaselwandle we- Indian ocean kunye ne-savanna.

Lo mthi unexabiso eliphakathi kwindawo yendalo njengoko unceda ekutsaleni izinambuzane ezizalisayo ezityalweni, unceda izilwanyana zasehlathini kunye neemfuyo ezitya amagqabi awo, kwaye iintaka zidla iziqhamo zawo.

Umthi lo awuzimeli—ukuthetha ukuba umthi ngamnye uvelisa iintyatyambo zesini esinye kuphela (ezisisidoda okanye ezibafazi), ngoko ukuxhomekeka kwezinzambuzane ekuzaleni kubalulekile (pollination).

Kubalulekile ukutyala imithi emininzi kufutshane ukuze kwandiswe amathuba okuvelisa isiqhamo.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

- Lo mthi ulungele imimandla efudumeleyo nephakathi kwamaqondo obushushu aphakathi kwe-10°C kunye ne-35°C.
- Ububanzi bemvula ephakathi yonyaka bufanelekile.
- Uhlala kamnandi elangeni ngokupheleleyo okanye emthunzini.
- Uyayinyamezela imbalela kunye neqabaka—yinto eguquguqukayo!

IMEKO YOMHLABA

- Umthi uthanda umhlaba oneentlabathi ezixubene nomhlaba othambileyo kwaye okhupha amanzi kakuhle.
- Ukhula kakuhle kumhlaba onepH ephakathi kwe-5 ukuya kwi-7.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

- Lo mthi ukhula embewini, efuna ukukrwitshwa okanye ukukrwelwa phambi kokutyala.
- Imbewu idla ngokuhluma phakathi kweeveki ezi-4 ukuya kwezi-8.
- Izithole kunye nemithi eselula ifuna amanzi aphakathi ukuze ikhule kakuhle.
- Ukhula kancinci, kodwa unokufikelela kwi-30cm ngonyaka.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/diospyros-whyteana>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes

UMTHONGWANE

Englerophytum natalense (L), Natal milkplum, silver-leaved milkplum (E), umthongwane (X)

Esi sityalo sifumaneka kunxweme lwaseMpuma Afrika emazantsi, kwaye sikhula kwiindawo zehlathi lemvela, emilanjeni, kwiimifudlana nakumahlathi akufuphi nolwandle, ukuya kubude obuyi-1,800m.

Iziqhamo zawo zincinci, malunga ne-1.5cm ubukhulu, kwaye ziveliswa ukusuka ngoNovemba ukuya kulanuwari, zityiwa ziluhlaza.

Lo mthi uhhlala uluhlaza unokukhula kwi-15m ubude, kwaye une-canopy ephakathi.

Ngenxa yenkqubo yengcambu ephakathi, umthi ungasetyenziselwa ukutyalwa kufuphi nezakhiwo kunye neendlela, kodwa akufuneki kufuphi nemibhobho yamanzi okanye imizila yombane ngenxa yobude bawo kunye namagqabi awaphalazayo.

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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Iziqhamo zawo ziqulethe i-vitamin C eninzi, efanayo neye apile, esisixhobo esibalulekileyo ekomelezeni amaseli omzimba nakwi immunity.

Zikwaneentsimbi ezifana nekalhsyam, intsimbi, kunye nepotasiyam, ezibalulekileyo ekomelezeni igazi, amathambo kunye nezihlunu.

Imixube yengcambu isetyenziswa ukunyanga izifo zesisu kunye neentlungu zesisu.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Umthi unokukhula ube ngumthi wexabiso eliphezulu ekwenzeni ithunzi, kwaye ungasetyenziselwa ukuthintela umoya omkhulu.

Umthi uneenkuni eziqinileyo nezihlala ixesha elide, ezisetyenziswa ekwenzeni iintsika zocingo lokubiyi, izixhobo, izinto zokwakha kunye nokubasa.

Lo mthi kwaye unokukhula kwiindawo ezinesithunzi, kwaye unokunyamezela iindawo ezinamanzi amileyo.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Iintyatyambo zawo zitsala izinambuzane, kubandakanya iinyosi kunye namabhabhathane, nto leyo ekutsaleni iintaka egadini.

Lo mthi ungasetyenziselwa ukulawula ukukhuliseka komhlaba ngendlela ephumeleleyo.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/englerophytum-natalense>

Imifanekiso: PlantZAfrica, Wikimedia Commons

UMTHONGWANE

Englerophyllum natalense (L), Natal milkplum (E), umthongwane (X)

Umthi uvela kunxweme lwaseMpuma Afrika emazantsi kwaye uqhele ukufumaneka kwiindawo ezinegrassland nakwi-savanna.

Ubalulekile ekutyiseni izilwanyana zasendle – iintaka ezifana ne-sunbird zitya iintyatyambo zawo, imibungu yeebhathane itya amagqabi awo, kwaye iziqhamo zityiwa ziinkawu, iihagu zasehlathini, kunye neentaka ezitya iziqhamo.

Esi sityalo sikhula kancinci, kwaye sidinga ukunyamekelwa ngokufumana amanzi aphakathi, isithunzi kunye nobushushu obufanelekileyo.

Ngenxa yokuba sitsala iintaka, izinambuzane kunye nezilwanyana zasendle, kungcono sityalwe kude nezakhiwo, ukuze kube nobudlelwane obuhle phakathi kwabantu kunye nendalo.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Umthi uthanda iindawo ezinemo yexesha eliphakathi kwaye unganamezela ubushushu obuphakathi kwe-10°C kunye ne-35°C.

Njengoko uthanda amanzi, uthanda iindawo ezinemvula eninzi.

Kungcono utyalwe kwindawo enesithunzi okanye ithunzana.

Akumelanga utyalwe kwiindawo ezibandayo kakhulu kuba ubuthathaka kwikhephu.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Umthi ukhula kwimihlaba ekwigumbi eliphakathi, enesanti enencindi kunye nemihlaba eneclay epholileyo, ekwazi ukubamba amanzi kakuhle.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Umthi unokuhlwayelwa kwimbewu entsha necocekileyo.

Imbewu ihluma ngokukhawuleza phakathi kweeveki ezi-2 ukuya kwezi-3.

Ungakhuliswa nakumasebe athathwe emithini emincinci aze apathwe ngehomoni, okanye usebenzise intonga.

Izithole kunye nezityalo ezincinci zifuna amanzi amaninzi rhoqo.

Lo mthi ukhula kancinci, malunga ne-300-400mm ngonyaka, kwaye ufikelela kubudala bokuvuthwa kwiminyaka emithandathu.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/englerophyllum-natalense>

Imifanekiso: PlantZAfrica, Wikimedia Commons

UMTHUMBU

Ficus sur (L), broom cluster fig (E), umthumbu, amakhiwane (X)

Umthumbu ufumaneka kulo lonke elaseMzantsi Afrika, ecaleni kwemilambo, kwiilathi ngasemlanjeni, kwilathi elivulekileyo nasehlathini leengca, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-2,500m.

Izihlumelo ziqhakaza kakhulu ngeengqokelela, ngalinye lijikeleze i-5cm ububanzi, kwaye zingatywa ziluhlaza okanye zomisiwe.

Lo mthi ukhula malunga ne-20m ukuphakama, unegqabi elibanzi kwaye uneengcambu ezinamandla nezingamisekileyo phantsi komhlaba.

Ngenxa yendlela okhula ngayo, kungcono uwuhlwanyele kwiindawo ezivulekileyo, kude neentambo zombane namanzi, izakhiwo kunye neendlela.

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUQHAMBA

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IMPILO NENDLELA YOKUTYA

Uqulethe ifayibha eninzi – ezalisa isisu kwaye ilungele inkqubo yokugaya ukutya.

Unayo ikhalsiyam, intsimbi (iron), kunye nefosforasi – eziqinisa amathambo negazi.

Isiqhamo singasetyenziswa ukwenza iijusi ezimnandi, iijem kunye nokugcinwa kwesidlo.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYARDINI

Uncedisa kwithunzi kubantu nezityalo ngenxa yobukhulu ne-canopy ebanzi.

Amasebe awo anakunika iinkuni ezithambileyo, ukwenza amagubu kunye nenkuni ezincinane.

Ulusu lwawo lunokusetyenziselwa ukwenza intambo kwaye luyasetyenziswa kunyango lwemveli.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Utsala izimbuzane ezincinane (wasps) ezithwala imbewu zisebenzisa izihlumelo zalo, ngaloo ndlela zancedisa ekuveliseni izityalo.

Iintaka zitya iziqhamo zawo lomthi, kunye nezinzambuzane ezisalwa ngumthi.

Izilwanyana ezifana namalulwane, neenkawu zitya iziqhamo zawo kwaye zisasaza imbewu yawo.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/ficus-sur>

Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, iSpotnature

UMTHUMBU

Ficus sur (L), broom cluster fig (E), umthumbu, amakhiwane (X)

Umthumbu uvela kwiNgingqi yaseMazantsi aseAfrika kwaye uyafumaneka kwiindawo ze-Albany thicket, fynbos, grassland, Indian Ocean coastal belt, Nama Karoo, savanna, kunye ne-Succulent Karoo.

Imibungu yamabhabhathane zidla amasebe okanye iingcambu zawo. Amalulwane, iintaka, ii-elephants, kunye neenkawu zithanda iziqhamo zawo ezivuthiweyo.

Ukuhanjiswa kwembewu kwenziwa ngamanxele ezithi zifake amaqanda azo ngaphakathi kwizihlumelo.

Umthi ukhula phakathi kwamasebe emithi emikhulu, emva koko uthumele iingcambu zawo emhlabeni.

Ngenxa yokuba utsala amanxele (wasps), qinisekisa ukuba uwuhlwayela okanye uwutyala kude nendlu.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Umthi utyeba kakuhle kumaqondo obushushu aphakathi kwe-16°C ne-21°C.

Ukhula kamnandi kwiindawo ezinemvula ephakathi kwe-800mm - 1,800mm nkonyaka.

Ufuna ilanga elipheleleyo kwaye uza kushiya isithunzi kwizityalo ezingaphantsi kwawo.

Uyakwazi ukumelana neqhwa elincinci, kodwa ufuna ukukhuselwa xa uselula.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Ukhula kakuhle kumhlaba onentlabathi, otyebileyo, kunye nomhlaba onodaka.

Iingcambu zawo ezinamandla zingafumana ukuzinza ngokukhawuleza, nkqu nasezindaweni ezinomoya okanye ezimanzi.

UKUYILIMA LE NTLOBO YOMTHI

Ungatyala ngokusebenzisa imbewu ecocekileyo, leyo ivelisa izihlumelo emva kweveki.

Unokukhuliswa nasekuhlutheni (cuttings) amasebe entlakohlaza.

Unkcenkeshele rhoqo kwiminyaka emine yokuqala kwiindawo ezinemvula embalwa; kodwa uyazinyamekela kwiindawo ezinemvula eninzi.

Ukhula malunga ne-0.5m ukuya kwi-1m nkonyaka, kwaye uqala ukuvuthwa emva kweminyaka emine.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:

<https://pza.sanbi.org/ficus-sur>

Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes, iSpotnature

UMVILO

Vangueria infausta (L), wild medlar (E), amavilo (X)

Lo mthi ufumaneka kulo lonke elingasezantsi-mpuma eMzantsi Afrika, kwiindawo ezineenduli, nakwiindawo ezivulekileyo zamahlathi, kananjalo kwiindawo ezinamatye nakwiindunduma zesanti, kwiindawo ezifika kwi-1,500m.

Iziqhamo eziyi-2cm zinencasa efana ne-apile, kwaye ziveliswa ukusukela ngoMatshi ukuya ku-Okthobha. Zityiwa ziluhlaza, ziphendulwa ijusi okanye i-jam.

Lo mthi mncinci ukhula ukuya kwi-5m, unegqabi eliphakathi ngobukhulu kwaye udla ngokuba nemithi emininzi ephantse yahlulwe kwisiqu esinye.

Inkqubo yengcambu ephakathi, ukuphakama kunye nesigqabi sakhe kuvumela ukuba utyalwe kufuphi nezakhiwo, iindlela kunye nezixhobo zombane.

IMPILO NOKUTYA

Isiqhamo sineVitamin C eninzi eyomeleza ukhuseleko lomzimba.

Sityebile ngecalcium, i-iron, i-magnesium kunye ne-potassium ezibalulekileyo kwimpilo yamathambo, igazi nomzimba.

Siqulathe ifayibha, iprotheni kunye ne-amino acids eziluncedo kwinkqubo yokwetyisa.

Iingcambu zisetyenziswa kunyango lwe-malaria kunye ne-pneumonia.

I-decoction yamagqabi asetyenziselwa ukucoca umzimba kwaye ekunyangelweni kweentlungu zamazinyo, zesisu nezamaxesha okuya exesheni.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Amagqabi omthi ayatyiwa yimfuyo njengokutya.

Umthi wawo usetyenziswa njengomthi wamaplanga, wenziwe izibonda zocingo kunye nezixhobo ezahlukeneyo.

Lo mthi womelele kwaye uyakwazi ukumelana nomkhenkce kunye nexesha elomileyo.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Lo mthi uyimithombo ebalulekileyo yokutya kwezindambuzane, iintaka kunye nezilwanyana ezinkulu.

Uyakwazi ukuzivumelanisa neemeko ezinzima kwaye afaneleke ekuthinteleni ukubola komhlaba.

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/vangueria-infausta>
 Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

UMVILO

Vangueria infausta (L), wild medlar (E), amavilo (X)

Umvilo uvela eAfrika kwaye ufumaneka kwi-biome yeAlbany Thicket, i-fynbos, imihlaba yeenduli zegusha, unxweme loLwandlekazi l- Indian ocean, iNama Karoo, i-savanna kunye ne-Succulent Karoo.

Lo mthi uxhasa inkqubo yendalo ngokunika ukutya kwimibungu yamabhabhathane ezityayo amagqabi, kwiinkawu nakwezinye izilwanyana ezincinci ezityayo iziqhamo, nakwi buck ezitya amagqabi.

Iintyatyambo zisasazwa zizinambuzane, kanti iimbewu zisasazwa ziintaka kunye neenkawu ezizityayo.

Ukutyalwa kwawo kwenzeka ngeembewu okanye ngezithole, kwaye iimbewu zingagcinwa de kube yiminyaka elandelayo.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YOKUKHULA

Lo mthi uthanda ukukhula kwiimeko ezithambileyo ukuya kweziphakathi kwezinga lokushisa, phakathi kwe-12°C ukuya kwi-36°C.

Ukhula kakuhle kwiindawo ezinemvula ephakathi kwe-700mm ukuya kwi-1,500mm ngonyaka.

Uthanda ukukhanya kwelanga ngokupheleleyo kodwa unokunyamezela umthunzi omncinci.

Uyakwazi ukuzivumelanisa neemeko ezinzima kwaye uyakwazi ukumelana nexesha elomileyo nomkhenkce.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Ukhula kakuhle kumhlaba onesanti kunye nomhlaba we-loam.

Uthanda umhlaba onepH ephakathi kwe-5 ne-7.5.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Unokukhuliswa ngeembewu ezintsha okanye ezo zigciniweyo, ezifanele ukutyalwa ehlotyeni.

Izithole ezisikiweyo eziphathwe ngehomonni zifunyanwa kumthi omdala ophakathi kokuqina, kwaye iimpunzi ezivela ezantsi komthi zikhula lula.

Izityalo ezitsha zifuna ukufumanisa amanzi aphaqathi.

Umthi ukhula ngobukhulu obuphakathi, malunga ne-50cm ngonyaka.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/vangueria-infausta>
 Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

UMVUTSHWAMA / UMYUSHULUBE

Canthium inerme (L), turkey berry (E), umvutshwama, umyushulube, umvuthwamini (X)

Lo mthi uqhele ukufumaneka eMzantsi Afrika kwiindidi ezahlukeneyo zeendawo eziphilayo, kuquka amahlathi aselunxwemeni nakwiinduli, amahlathi akumhlaba oneenduli, imida yamahlathi, i-bushveld kunye neengca ezinamawa, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-1,700m.

Iziqhamo zalo mthi zivela ngamaxhama, ngalinye lilingana ne-1cm ngobukhulu, kwaye zidliwa zintsha.

Lo mthi ukhula ukuya kubude obuyi-14m kwaye unomthunzi ophakathi.

Ngenxa yendlela okhula ngayo emodareyithiweyo kunye nenkqubo yeengcambu engaphazamisiyo, ungatyalwa kufutshane nemigca yombane namanzi, nakufuphi nezakhiwo neendlela.

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Isiqhamo salo mthi sisisityalo esilungileyo seevithamini C ne-E, eziluncedo kwisikhumba, amathambo, kunye nokomeleza amasosha omzimba.

Iqulethe izixhobo zokulandela umkhondo ezingaqhelekanga ezibalulekileyo kwimisebenzi emininzi yomzimba.

Amagqabi awo ngamanye amaxesha asetyenziswa kunyango lwezifo zesisu.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Lo mthi uyindawo efanelekileyo yokuthintela umoya kunye nokunika izilwanyana ezifuywayo isikhusele.

Iinkuni zawo zomelele kakhulu kwaye zisetyenziswa ukwenza iintsika zocingo, ifenitshala, kunye nezixhobo.

Ukuba sisityalo esihlala siluhlaza amagqabi anyaka wonke kunye nobuhle bamagqabi aso, utsala iintaka kunye nezinambuzane unyaka wonke.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Ngenxa yameva awo amakhulu kunye nobume obumxinwa, ungasetyenziswa njengothango olumileyo ukuthintela izilwanyana ezifuywayo ukuba zingangeni.

Ungamelana neemeko ezinzima kwaye uyaxhathisa imbalela.

Lo mthi ukhula ngokukhawuleza kwaye ungasetyenziswa ukulawula ukukrazuka komhlaba.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/canthium-inerme>
 Imifanekiso: Wikimedia Commons,
 iNaturalist

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UMVUTSHWAMA / UMYUSHULUBE

Canthium inerme (L), turkey berry (E), umvutshwama, umyushulube, umvuthwamini (X)

Lo mthi uvela eMzantsi Afrika kwaye usasazeke kakuhle kulo mmandla. Uqhele ukufumaneka kwi-biomes ezifana ne-fynbos, iinduli ezinezityalo ezifutshane, i-savanna, i-Nama Karoo, kunye ne-Succulent Karoo.

Uxabiseke kakhulu kwi-ecology, nto leyo emenza abe sisityalo esibalulekileyo kwii-gadi.

Iintyatyambo zawo zibonelela nge-pollen kunye ne-nectar kwiinyosi, kwaye iziqhamo zidliwa ziintaka kunye neehagu zasendle.

Lo mthi uthuthwa zizinambuzane, kwaye imbewu yawo isasazwa ziintaka ezitya iziqhamo zawo. Imbewu ingakhutshwa ngokususa inyama kwizityalo ezivuthileyo.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Zinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Lo mthi ukhula kakuhle kwimimandla eneqondo eliphakathi lemvela kwaye unokunyamezela ukufuma okuncinci.

Uthanda ukukhanya kwelanga elipheleleyo kodwa angakhula kwindawo enethunzi elincinane.

Lo mthi unokumelana nomkhenkce omncinci.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Lo mthi uyahlengahlengiswa kwaye ukhula kakuhle kwisanti, udongwe, kunye ne-loam.

Ungakhula kumhlaba onepH oyi-acid, ophakathi, okanye onealkali.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Lo mthi kulula ukuwukhulisa, kwaye ungatyalwa kwimbewu yesiqhamo esivuthiweyo kwaye icoceke.

Ukuntshula kwayo kungathatha iinyanga ezi-2 ukuya kwezi-3, emva koko ukhula ngokukhawuleza.

Ngelixa iselula, gcina izithole zifumile, kodwa ingabi manzi kakhulu.

Vumela izithole zikhule kangangeeveki ezi-2 ukuya kwezi-3 phambi kokuzityala emhlabeni.

Lo mthi ukhula ngokukhawuleza, ufikelela kumamitha ambalwa kwiminyaka embalwa.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/canthium-inerme>
 Imifanekiso: Wikimedia Commons,
 iNaturalist

UTHONGOTHI

Hyperacanthus amoenus (L), thorny gardenia (E), uthongothi (X)

Esi sityalo sifumaneka kunxweme olusempuma yoMzantsi Afrika, siqhele ukufumaneka kwiinduli ezivulekileyo, emahlathini aphakathi, kwiikloof ezimanzi nasemahlathini.

Iziqhamo zaso zihlala nganye, zimalunga ne-1.5cm ububanzi, ziveliswa ukusukela ngoMatshi ukuya kuOkthobha kwaye zityiwa zingaphekwanga.

Esisihlahla sikhula sifikelele kwi-3m, sinamasebe amaninzi, kwaye amasebe aso akhula ngokuthe tye kumqolo.

Ngenxa yesantya esiphakathi sokukhula kunye nenqanaba eliphantsi lengcambu kunye neendleko zamagqabi awileyo, esisihlahla silungele ukutyalwa kufutshane nezakhiwo, iindlela, imibhobho yamanzi nemigca yamandla.

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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Iziqhamo ziqulathe i-antioxidants ezininzi ezixhasa impilo entle kunye nokuphilisa.

Iingcambu neziqhamo zisetyenziswa kunyango lwemveli ukunyanga izifo zesisu kunye nokucoca umzimba.

Esi sityalo ngamanye amaxesha sisetyenziswa ekunyangeni umkhuhlane.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Umthi wawo usetyenziselwa ukwenza i-fibre, izibonda zocingo, izixhobo ezincinci kunye neenkuni zomlilo.

Ukuba siphungulwa rhoqo, amasebe aso anameva namasebe aminxeneyo enza ucingo oluhle lokhuseleko okanye udonga lwendalo.

Amagqabi aluhlaza aqaqambileyo kunye neentyatyambo ezimhlophe ezinevumba eliminandi zenza ukuba sibe sisityalo esithandwayo sokuhombisa.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Sisityalo esibalulekileyo somthombo we-nectar kwizinambuzane, ngakumbi iinyosi, kwaye iziqhamo zaso zidlwa ziintaka.

Singatyalwa njengocingo oluphilayo ukuze kuthintelwe izilwanyana zasekhaya ekungeneni.

Amagqabi aso adliwa ziindidi ezininzi zezilwanyana zasendle.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela: <https://pza.sanbi.org/hyperacanthus-amoenus>

Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

UTHONGOTHI

Hyperacanthus amoenus (L), thorny gardenia (E), uthongothi (X)

Esi sityalo sivela eMzantsi Afrika kwaye sifumaneka kakhulu kumgangatho wonxweme loLwandlekazi lwe-Indian ocean nakwi-savanna.

Siyancedisa kwinkqubo yendalo njengomthombo wokutya kwiintaka nakwinkawu ezityayo iziqhamo zaso, kunye nezilwanyana ezidla amagqabi aso.

Ukuchumiselwa kwaso kwenziwa zizinambuzane, kuquka iinyosi kunye neempukane ezincinci, kwaye imbewu yaso isasazwa ziintaka nezilwanyana.

Ngenxa yokuba itsala izilwanyana ezahlukeneyo, kungcono ukuyityala kude nekhaya ukuze kugcinwe ubuhlobo obuhle nezilwanyana zasendle.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

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IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

- Esisihlahla silungele kakhulu imozulu yetropiki kunye ne-subtropiki ephakathi kwe-10°C ne-35°C.
- Sikhula kakuhle kwiindawo ezinemvula ephakathi ehlotyeni.
- Sithanda ukukhula kwiindawo ezinomthunzi okanye umthunzi omncinci, kodwa sinokunyamezela nokukhanya kwelanga ngokupheleleyo.
- Sisityalo esiqinileyo esikwazi ukumelana nembalela kwaye sikwakwazi ukuthwala umkhenkce ophakathi.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

- Sithanda umhlaba wohlobo lwe-loam kwaye sikwakwazi ukumelana nayo nayiphi na imihlaba ephuma kakhule amanzi kwaye igcina ukufuma okuthile.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

- Imbewu kufuneka icocwe ngaphambi kokutyalwa.
- Ukuhluma kuthatha malunga neveki ezisi-8 kwaye amazinga empumelelo aphantsi.
- Ukusika imithana evela kwisityalo esivuthiweyo uze uyiphathise iihomoni kungakhokelela kwimpumelelo engcono.
- Izityalo ezincinci kunye neembewu mazifumane amanzi amaninzi.
- Ukukhula kancinci, malunga ne-50cm ngonyaka, kwaye sifikelela ekuvuthweni emva kweminyaka emi-3.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/hyperacanthus-amoenus>

Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

UYAWAYEAWAYE

Hoslundia opposita (L), orange bird berry, bird gooseberry, butterberry (E), uyaweyawe (X)

Esi sityalo sixhaphake kulo lonke elaseMzantsi Afrika kwaye sifumaneka kwi-savanna, emilanjani nakwiindawo eziluhlaza ezikufuphi, ukuya kubude obuyi-1,500m.

Iziqhamo zaso zincinci, malunga ne-0.6cm ubukhulu, kwaye ziveliswa ngobuninzi ukusuka ngo-Okthobha ukuya ku-Aprili, zityiwa ziluhlaza.

Esi sityalo sinokukhula siphantsi kwaye sinokuhamba, kodwa asidluli kubude obuyi-1m.

Ngenxa yokukhula kwaso okuthobekileyo, ingcambu ezinganweniyo kunye nesivuno esikhulu seziqhamo, sifaneleke kakhulu kufutshane nezindlu, izikolo, imibhobho yamanzi, kunye nemizila yombane.

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IMPILO NOKUTYA

Iziqhamo ziqulethe ii-antioxidants ezininzi ezinciphisa ukonakala kweeseli zomzimba kwaye zixhasa impiilo entle.

Amagqabi kunye neziqhamo aqulethe ii-phytochemicals ezinokukhupha iiyile ezibalulekileyo ezinokusetyenziswa kunyango lwezifo.

Amagqabi amancinci athambileyo ayaphekwa kwaye atyiwe njengemifino.

Amagqabi asetyenziswa njengesixhobo sokunyanga umkhuhlane, kunye nokukhuthaza ukugaya kakuhle.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Umthi omfutshane, onehlathi elihle elikhazimlayo kunye neziqhamo ezimibalabala, sisityalo esifanelekileyo sokuhlobisa iigadi, kwaye njengehedji.

Amagqabi awo anevumba elingathandekiyo eligoxtha iinyosi, nto leyo eyenza alungele ekusetyenziseni ukufumana ubusi kwiinyosi.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Iintyatyambo zivakashelwa kakhulu zii-nyosi, kwaye iziqhamo zityiwa ziintaka kunye nezilwanyana.

Amagqabi asetyenziswa yimibungu yeebhathathane njengokutya kwawo.

Isakhono saso sokukhula kwimihlaba enamatyhe okanye isanti sincipeda ekuzinziseni umhlaba nokulawula ukukhukuliseka.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/hoslundia-opposita>
 Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, Random Harvest, Wikimedia Commons

UYAWAYEAWAYE

Hoslundia opposita (L), orange bird berry, bird gooseberry, butterberry (E), uyaweyawe (X)

Esi sityalo sivala e-Afrika kwaye sifumaneka kunxweme lwe-Indian Ocean nakwi-savanna biomes.

Sibalulekile ekuxhaseni iintlobo ngeentlobo zezinto eziphilayo njengoko sisetyenziswa njengokutya: imibungu yeebhhabhathane itya amagqabi, iinyosi kunye nezinye izinambuzane zitya i-nectar, kwaye iintaka kunye nezilwanyana zitya iziqhamo.

Esi sityalo sisasazwa ziinyosi, kwaye imbewu yaso ihanjiswa ziintaka kunye nezilwanyana ezityayo iziqhamo.

Ngenxa yokuba itsala izinambuzane, iintaka kunye nezilwanyana, kungcono sityalwe kude nezindlu ukuze kube nobudlelwane obuhle phakathi kwabantu nendalo.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

IMEKO YOKUKHULA KWINDALO

Isityalo sithanda imozulu efudumeleyo, ye-tropiki kunye ne-sub-tropiki, phakathi kwe-20°C kunye ne-35°C.

Simele sityalwe kwiindawo ezinemvula ephakathi ukuya kweninzi.

Senza kakuhle kwiindawo ezishushu kwaye sifuna ukukhanya kwelanga ngokupheleleyo.

Asifanelanga kwiindawo ezibandayo ezinomkhenkce.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Sikhula kakuhle kwimihlaba eyahlukeneyo enesanti ephuma kakuhle amanzi.

Sithanda i-pH ephakathi kwe-5 kunye ne-7 (neutral).

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA ISITYALO

Imbewu entsha etyalwa phakathi kuka-Novemba no-Matshi ihluma ngokulula phakathi kweeveki ezi-2 nezi-4.

Ingakhuliswa nangokusika amasebe omthi ziphathwe ngehomon, ezihluma lula.

Izithole kunye nezityalo eziselula zifuna amanzi amaninzi.

Ukukhula kwaso kuphakathi, kwaye ukusika rhoqo kuya kunceda ukugcina imo yaso kwaye kukhuthaze ukukhula okutsha.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/hoslundia-opposita>
 Imifanekiso: iNaturalist, Random Harvest,
 Wikimedia Commons

WE-TRANVAAL RED MILKWOOD

Mimusops zeyheri (L), Transvaal red milkwood, red milkwood (E)

Lo mthi ufumaneka kwiindawo ezishushu nakumantla eMzantsi Afrika, kwiinduli ezinamatye, kwiinxweme zemilambo, emacaleni ehlathi, nakumahlathi avulekileyo kunye ne-bushveld eyomileyo.

Iziqhamo ezingange-1cm, zihluma ngamaqela ukusuka ngoAprili ukuya kuSeptemba kwaye zityiwa zingaphekhwanga.

Lo mthi ungakhula ufinyelele kwi-8m, une canopy engekho nkulu.

Ngenxa yeengcambu zawo azinabundlongondlongo kunye nesantya esiphakathi sokukhula, lo mthi unokutyalwa kufutshane nemibhobho yamanzi nakwizithuba zoluntu.

IXESHA LOKUQHAMBA				
Dec	Jan	Feb	☀️	
Mar	Apr	May	🍂	
Jun	Jul	Aug	❄️	
Sep	Oct	Nov	🍁	

IMPILO NOKUTYA

Iziqhamo ziqulethe iVitamin C eninzi, elinganayo nefumaneka kwiorenji, efanelekileyo ekomelezeni impilo kunye nokhuselo lomzimba.

Iqulethe i-calcium, i-phosphorus kunye ne-potassium eziphucula impilo yamathambo, igazi kunye neeseli zomzimba.

Ine-amino acids ezifunwa zizo zonke iiseli (cells) zomzimba ukuze zisebenze kakuhle.

Ixolo lomthi liyaphekwa ukwenza amayeza okusetyenziswa ekunyangeni amanxeba kunye nezilonda.

EZINDAWENI ZOKULIMA NASEMAYADINI

Lo mthi omkhulu ongatyhafiyo unokukhula ube ngumthunzi obalulekileyo okanye utyalwe njengomqobo womoya.

Umthi wawo usetyenziselwa ukwenza izibonda zocingo kunye nezixhobo.

Ngenxa yamagqabi awo aluhlaza aqaqambileyo, ingaphezulu lawo elihle kunye neentyatyambo ezimnandi, ngumthi othandwayo wokuhombisa.

UKUNCEDA INDALO

Lo mthi utsala iintaka ezininzi, izinambuzane kunye nezilwanyana ezityayo iziqhamo zawo kwaye zisasaza imbewu yawo.

Ungasetyenziswa ukulawula ukukrweleka komhlaba kwiindawo ezonakeleyo.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

Ngolwazi oluthe vetshe, ndwendwela:
<https://pza.sanbi.org/mimusops-zeyheri>
 Imifanekiso: Glenice Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

WE-TRANVAAL RED MILKWOOD

Mimusops zeyheri (L), Transvaal red milkwood, red milkwood (E)

Lo mthi uvela kwiindawo ezishushu nasemantla eMzantsi Afrika. Ufumaneka kunxweme loLwandlekazi l- Indian ocean nakwi-savanna.

Ngumthombo obalulekileyo wezinto eziphilayo njengoko unikezela ukutya kwiintaka, iinkawu kunye nee- antelope ezityayo iziqhamo, kunye nemibungu yamabhabhathane etyayo amagqabi.

Iintyatyambo zawo zisasazwa zizinambuzane, kwaye imbewu yaso isasazwa ziintaka kunye nezilwanyana ezityayo iziqhamo.

Ukutyeba kwesiqhamo kutsala izilwanyana ezininzi, ngoko kungcono ukutyalwa kude nekhaya.

Ubudlelwane kwindalo

Izinto ekufuneka uziqwalasele

IXESHA LOKUTYALA

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

IMEKO YEMOZULU NOKUKHULA

Lo mthi uthanda imozulu ephakathi kwe-15°C ne-25°C.

Ulungele kakhulu iindawo ezinemvula ephantsi unyaka wonke.

Uthanda ukukhanya kwelanga ngokupheleleyo kodwa uyakwazi ukunyamezela umthunzi omncinci.

Ubuthathaka kumkhenkce, ngoko kufuneka ukhuseleke kwiindawo ezibandayo.

IMEKO YOMHLABA

Lo mthi uyakhula kwimihlaba eyahlukeneyo emdaka kakuhle.

Ukhetha umhlaba onepH ephakathi kwe-5 ne-7.

INDLELA YOKUKHULISA

Imbewu entsha etyalwe kwangoko iyakwazi ukuhluma kakuhle.

Imbewu egciniweyo ihluma ngcono ukuba ikhuhliwe phambi kokutyalwa.

Imbewu ihluma ngokukhawuleza, ithatha malunga neeveki ezi-2.

Izityalo ezincinci kunye neembewu mazifumane amanzi amaninzi.

Lo mthi ukhula ngokukhawuleza kwaye ufikelela ekuvuthweni emva kweminyaka emi-3.

Xa uqokelela imbewu, yenza ngononophelo ukuphepha ukonakalisa isityalo. Ungathathi zonke iziqhamo ukuze umthi uqhubeke uvelisa.

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